

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation
in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

**Good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages
and other direct costs in regional governance scale**

Deliverable 3.5

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	D3.5 - Good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages and other direct costs in the regional governance scale
Work Package	WP3 – Envisioning transformative pathways for the demonstrators
Dissemination Level	Public
Author(s)	NCSR: Stelios Karozis, Ioannis Zarikos, Athanasios Sfetsos
Primary Contact and Email	Stelios Karozis, skarozis@ipta.demokritos.gr
Date Due	31/03/2024
Date Submitted	Version 1 (31/07/2024) Version 2 (02/07/2025) - After addressing comments from the external reviewers.
File Name	
Status	Version 1 (first submission of deliverable) Version 2 (version after addressing comments from the external reviewers)
Reviewed by (if applicable)	PIK: Fred Hattermann
Suggested citation	S. Karozis, I. Zarikos, A. Sfetsos (2025) Good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages and other direct costs in regional governance scale. TransformAR Deliverable 3.5, H2020 grant no. 101036683

© TransformAR Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original, unpublished work except when indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorised if the source is acknowledged.

This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAR. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. CURRENT BEST PRACTICES AND GUIDELINES	7
Evolution of Best Practices and Guidelines for avoiding damages	7
Frameworks and Standards	8
Key Principles and Components.....	10
Challenges and Opportunities	15
Future Directions	16
3. AVOID DAMAGES FRAMEWORK IN TRANSFORMAR	17
Overall concept and method	17
4. AVOIDED DAMAGES ASSESSMENT: HIGH DATA AVAILABILITY – KPI BASED	18
The case study of Municipality of Egaleo (MOE)	18
The case study of Gjøvik	26
5. AVOIDED DAMAGES ASSESSMENT: SPARSE DATA – HIGH-LEVEL APPROACH	35
The case study of West Country region.....	35
The case study of City of Lappeenranta	41
6. GOOD AND BEST PRACTICES GUIDELINES FOR AVOIDING DAMAGES	46
7. CONCLUSIONS	50
REFERENCES	51
ANNEX I: DEMONSTRATORS PROFILE.....	53
Municipality of Egaleo.....	53
Lappeenranta.....	55
Westcountry Region	58
ANNEX II: CLIMATE ANALYSIS PLOT USED IN SPARSE DATA APPROACH.....	61
West Country region	61
City of Lappeenranta	66

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current deliverable is type “Report”, and this document summarizes the main elements of Task 3.3 towards the development of a framework for best practices and guidelines for avoiding damages and other direct costs in regional governance scale. The experience and knowledge gained from the demonstrators are used to produce a guideline of good practices, to diffuse the results and render them usable and useful in other cases.

The guidelines for good practices are based on the experience and knowledge gained from D3.4 and by bringing the participatory approaches and qualitative and technical contribution at demonstrator scale.

As a follow-up to the recommendations received in the context of the second project review (February 2025), the document was restructure complementary to D3.4. D3.4 is focusing on the methodologies developed to assess the avoided damages (D3.5 methodology parts was moved to D3.4 and new sparse data approach is introduced), whereas D3.5 focuses on the application and best practices.

In TransformAr context, avoided damages represent the quantification of potential effectiveness of solutions implemented at demonstrator level to cope with climate change risks. More specifically, avoided damages are the benefits derived from mitigation and adaptation efforts that reduce potential adverse impacts of climate change. The framework distinguishes between climate change damages (adverse effects that cannot be adequately mitigated or adapted to) and avoided damages (benefits of effective adaptation efforts that prevent potential future impacts). The assessment compares two scenarios: the baseline situation (current conditions with or without solutions) and future climate change scenarios, with the difference between these states defining the avoided damages

In order to accommodate different capacity of relevant actors to provide information and data, two methods were developed. The High Data Availability - KPI Based Approach quantifies climate hazards and their impacts using an extensive list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across impact categories, whereas, the Sparse Data - High Level Approach was developed to address situations with limited data availability, following the established IPCC risk assessment framework. The High data availability approach was applied in Municipality of Egaleo demonstrator and Gjøvik replicator, whereas the Sparse data availability was applied in Lappeenranta and West Country demonstrators. Both methodologies yields similar results but with different data types and analysis, with the new Sparse data approach being more convenient to apply thus more generalised. Below the main outcomes of the assessment is presented.

Demonstrator	Approach	Main Hazards	Short-term Avoided Damages	Long-term Avoided Damages
Municipality of Egaleo	High Data KPI	Heatwaves	-11.0%	-26.0% to -35.8% (RCP4.5 to RCP8.5)
Gjøvik	High Data KPI	Flooding	-23.6%	47.1% (SSP1.26) 47.6% (SSP3.7) 48.1%(SSP5.85)
Lappeenranta	Sparse Data	Flooding	639,600.0€	1,868,152.0€ (SSP1.26) 4,670,380.0€ (SSP5.85)
West Country Region	Sparse Data	Drought	820,000€	3,540,000€ (SSP1.26) 6,440,000€ (SSP5.85)

Moreover, an approach on how to apply the approach of avoided damages assessment in the decision making of potential new actors, was introduced based on the experience gained in TransformAR project.

1. Introduction

Climate change **damages** refer to the adverse effects of climate change impacts that cannot be mitigated or adapted effectively. These damages encompass a wide range of effects, including loss of land and property, health and ecological damages, threats to human security, and economic impacts. The term "loss and damage" is often used to describe these impacts, particularly those that are beyond the capacity of mitigation and adaptation efforts. Such damages can include both sudden-onset disasters (like hurricanes and floods) and slow-onset processes (such as sea-level rise and desertification) (Geest, et al. 2019) (Voigt 2008). **Avoided damages** refer to the benefits derived from mitigation and adaptation efforts that reduce the potential adverse impacts of climate change. These benefits are essentially the costs that would have been incurred had no action been taken to address climate change. Effective mitigation strategies, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and adaptation measures, like building flood defences, contribute to avoiding significant economic, social, and environmental damages. For instance, integrating climate science with economic models helps estimate the monetary value of avoided damages, showing that mitigation can prevent substantial costs associated with extreme weather events and other climate impacts (Hsiang et al 2017) (Kooten, et al. 2013).

In 'D3.4 - Tools on the avoided damages and benefits per demo', a framework assessing the effectiveness of TransformAr solutions was introduced, building on the concept of avoided damages. The framework is based on quantifying effectiveness and damages qualitatively or quantitatively using a list of key performance indicators (KPIs). The assessment is performed for the current situation, future scenarios, and before and after the solution implementation. By comparison of quantified values with and without the implementation of a planned solution for a set of climate scenarios, the assessment provides an estimation of the climate-avoided damages.

In the current approach, the framework was expanded and further developed to define the concept of damages and avoided damages more clearly, based on discussions with the demonstrators and technical partners and the experience we gained via the interaction with the demonstrators and the barriers we had to surpass. The deliverable explores current best practices and guidelines that directly or indirectly tackle the concept of avoiding damages in climate change, presents the avoided damages assessment developed in TransformAr alongside the complete case of Municipality of Egaleo (MOE) and provides a stepped guide to replicate the process beyond the project.

2. Current Best Practices and Guidelines

Climate change adaptation strategies have led to the emergence of promising strategies for addressing pressing environmental challenges while fostering sustainable development. As the demand for adaptation approaches grows, understanding the current landscape of best practices and guidelines for avoiding damages becomes increasingly crucial. This section comprehensively reviews the state of the art in climate adaptation best practices and guidelines, drawing insights from recent literature, expert opinions, and practical experiences.

Evolution of Best Practices and Guidelines for avoiding damages

The evolution of best practices and recommendations, on the application of a variety of solution (NBS, digital, etc.), shows continuous learning, innovation, and adaptation to new environmental and societal concerns. These adaptation measures have evolved from a conservation and restoration idea to a complete approach considering ecological, social, and economic factors. These best practices and standards have evolved through numerous vital stages, each with a focus, techniques, and goals shift.

Initially, best practices and guidelines for avoiding damages arose in reaction to environmental degradation and biodiversity loss, emphasising the significance of protecting and restoring natural ecosystems to address current conservation issues. These early guidelines emphasised themes like ecosystem integrity, connectedness, and resilience, advocating for the protection of essential habitats, the restoration of degraded landscapes, and the enhancement of biodiversity through targeted conservation efforts. These principles provided the groundwork, such as incorporating NBS into larger environmental management strategies and policies by prioritising ecological objectives.

As knowledge of the connection between ecosystems and human well-being grew, best practices and guidelines for avoiding damages began incorporating social and economic factors into decision-making processes. This transition mirrored an awareness of the numerous benefits of adaptation interventions for both people and the environment, ranging from increasing climate resilience and minimising natural hazards to boosting public health and supporting local livelihoods. Guidelines for climate change adaptation begin to highlight ideas such as multifunctionality, participative approaches, and inclusion, advocating for incorporating multiple viewpoints and values into their design and implementation.

Furthermore, developments in scientific research, technology innovation, and policy development have all contributed to establishing best practices for climate adaptation. New methodologies, tools, and approaches have been created to evaluate climate adaptation interventions' efficacy, scalability, and sustainability, allowing practitioners to make better decisions and prioritise actions that optimise positive outcomes. Guidelines for climate adaptation measures are becoming more evidence-based, using transdisciplinary knowledge and empirical evidence to inform decision-making and support adaptive management methods.

More recently, the evolution of climate adaptation measures best practices has been marked by an increased emphasis on cross-sector collaboration and partnership formation. Recognising the need for integrated and collaborative solutions to complex environmental and socioeconomic concerns, Climate adaptation guidelines have aimed to stimulate collaboration across a wide range of stakeholders, including government agencies, civil society organisations, academia, and the commercial sector. This emphasis on partnership-building reflects an understanding of the

importance of collective action and shared responsibility in solving global environmental concerns such as climate change, biodiversity loss, urbanisation, and natural resource management.

The evolution of climate adaptation measures best practices is likely to be influenced by continued advances in research, technology, policy, and practice. As climate adaptation measures, such as NBS among other, gain traction as a mainstream method to tackling environmental and societal concerns, its recommendations are projected to become increasingly sophisticated, context-specific, and adaptable to a wide range of geographic, cultural, and socioeconomic circumstances. By embracing innovation, cooperation, and learning-oriented approaches, the evolution of climate adaptation measures best practices hold the prospect of unleashing nature's full potential to create more sustainable, resilient, and inclusive communities for future generations.

Frameworks and Standards

A number of frameworks and standards have been developed to assist in the design, implementation, and assessment of climate adaptation and mitigation solutions. These frameworks were designed based on local policies, climatic conditions, and local applicability of solutions.

International

International frameworks play a crucial role in guiding and coordinating global efforts to adapt to climate change. One of the most prominent frameworks is the **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)** (Kuyper et al., 2018; Mantlana et al., 2024), which established the foundational legal and institutional structures for global climate policy. Under the UNFCCC, the **Paris Agreement** stands out as a landmark international treaty adopted in 2015, aimed at limiting global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels while pursuing efforts to limit the increase to 1.5°C. This agreement mandates countries to submit and update Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) that outline their mitigation and adaptation commitments. To support adaptation, the Paris Agreement encourages the development of **National Adaptation Plans (NAPs)**, which help countries identify their medium- and long-term adaptation needs and develop strategies to address them. Solutions and interventions under NAPs often include enhancing early warning systems, climate-resilient infrastructure, and sustainable water management practices.

The **Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)** also significantly influences climate adaptation strategies through its comprehensive Assessment Reports, which provide scientific evaluations of climate change impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability (Palutikof et al., 2023). These reports, including the Special Reports on global warming of 1.5°C and the impacts on land and oceans, offer essential scientific guidance for policymakers. The IPCC emphasizes the need for integrating climate adaptation into all levels of planning and policy, promoting solutions such as nature-based solutions, ecosystem-based adaptation, and the use of climate-resilient agricultural practices to secure food production and protect biodiversity. Complementing these efforts, the **Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030** focuses on reducing disaster risks and building resilience to both natural and human-induced hazards. It emphasizes the importance of integrating disaster risk reduction and climate adaptation measures, advocating for interventions like improved building codes, land-use planning that considers future climate risks, and community-based disaster preparedness programs. These measures aim to mitigate the impact of extreme weather events and reduce vulnerability in high-risk areas. The **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, particularly **Goal 13 (Climate Action)**, further reinforce the need for urgent action to combat climate change and its

impacts, highlighting the interconnectedness of climate adaptation with broader sustainable development objectives. Solutions promoted under Goal 13 include transitioning to renewable energy sources, promoting energy efficiency, and fostering innovation in green technologies. Additionally, the SDGs advocate for climate education and awareness, strengthening institutional capacities to manage climate risks, and ensuring that vulnerable communities receive adequate support to adapt to changing climate conditions. Combined, these international frameworks provide a cohesive and comprehensive structure for countries to develop, implement, and monitor their climate adaptation strategies. They ensure that efforts are scientifically informed, globally coordinated, and aligned with sustainable development goals. By promoting a range of solutions and interventions, these frameworks aim to enhance resilience, protect ecosystems, and secure livelihoods against the adverse impacts of climate change.

European Adaptation strategy

The **European Union Adaptation Strategy** serves as a comprehensive framework guiding member states in enhancing resilience and reducing vulnerability to the impacts of climate change across Europe. Adopted in 2013 and updated in 2021, the strategy emphasizes the integration of climate adaptation into all relevant EU policies and funding programs, fostering a holistic and cohesive approach to adaptation. A vital strategy component is promoting **nature-based solutions**, such as restoring wetlands, reforesting degraded areas, and creating green urban spaces, which not only enhance biodiversity but also provide natural defences against floods, heatwaves, and other climate impacts (Remling, 2018; Rutherford et al., 2020). The strategy also focuses on **climate-resilient infrastructure**, advocating for including climate considerations in designing, constructing, and maintaining buildings, roads, and other critical infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events. To support the agricultural sector, the EU Adaptation Strategy encourages adopting **climate-smart farming practices**, including crop diversification, soil conservation techniques, and efficient water management systems, ensuring sustainable food production under changing climate conditions. Additionally, the strategy underscores the importance of **early warning systems** and improved **risk assessment tools** to better predict and respond to climate-related hazards, thereby protecting communities and economies (Rutherford et al., 2020). The strategy also aims to enhance **financial support mechanisms** by leveraging funds from the EU budget, such as the European Structural and Investment Funds, to invest in adaptation projects. Furthermore, the strategy promotes **knowledge sharing and capacity building** through platforms like the Climate-ADAPT portal, which facilitates the exchange of information and best practices among member states, regions, and cities. By prioritising these adaptation solutions, the EU Adaptation Strategy seeks to build a climate-resilient Europe that can effectively manage and mitigate the diverse and evolving challenges of climate change (European Commission, 2021).

National and regional scale

National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) are essential instruments developed under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) framework, aimed at helping countries, particularly developing nations, identify their medium- and long-term adaptation needs and formulate comprehensive strategies to address climate change impacts. Initiated in 2010 during the UNFCCC's Cancun Adaptation Framework, NAPs are designed to enhance nations' adaptive capacity and resilience by systematically assessing vulnerabilities and integrating climate adaptation into national policies and planning processes. NAPs emphasize various adaptation solutions tailored to each

country's specific climatic, economic, and social contexts. One of the key solutions is the development and implementation of **climate-resilient agricultural practices**, including crop diversification, improved irrigation techniques, and drought-resistant crop varieties. These practices aim to secure food production due to changing precipitation patterns and increasing temperatures (Leiter, 2021). Another critical component of NAPs is the enhancement of **water resource management**. This involves measures such as constructing reservoirs and rainwater harvesting systems, restoring natural water bodies, and implementing efficient water use technologies to address water scarcity and variability. **Infrastructure adaptation** is also a priority, with NAPs advocating for the design and construction of buildings, roads, and other infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events such as floods, storms, and heatwaves. **Ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA)** is another significant focus within NAPs, promoting the conservation and restoration of ecosystems that provide natural buffers against climate impacts. For example, mangroves and wetlands can mitigate coastal erosion and storm surges, while forests can stabilize soils and regulate water cycles. NAPs also stress the importance of enhancing **early warning systems** and **disaster risk management**. These solutions involve establishing monitoring and forecasting systems for extreme weather events and community-based disaster preparedness and response plans to reduce the risk and impact of natural disasters. **Urban adaptation measures** are also prioritized, encouraging the development of green spaces, improving drainage systems, and incorporating climate considerations into urban planning to reduce the urban heat island effect and manage stormwater. Furthermore, NAPs advocate for integrating **climate adaptation into national development policies and sectoral plans**, ensuring a coordinated approach across different levels of government and sectors. This includes mainstreaming adaptation into health, education, and social protection policies to build overall societal resilience. Finally, **capacity building and knowledge sharing** are fundamental aspects of NAPs, aiming to strengthen institutional capacities, enhance technical skills, and promote the exchange of best practices and lessons learned among countries and regions. International cooperation and funding mechanisms, such as the Green Climate Fund, often support this, which provides financial resources to developing countries for implementing their NAPs (Leiter, 2021).

Key Principles and Components

The key principles of the frameworks and standards, regardless of the application scale (global, transnational, and national/regional). Common themes and principles underpinning climate adaptation measures best practices and guidelines include:

Site selection and design principles that prioritise ecosystem integrity, connectivity, and resilience.

Climate adaptation measures are creative methods to tackle complex environmental and societal concerns that capitalise on natural systems' inherent resilience and efficiency. Common themes and ideas that drive NBS best practices and standards for site selection and design underscore the necessity of addressing ecosystem integrity, connectivity, and resilience. These concepts are critical for maintaining climate adaptation activities' efficacy, sustainability, and long-term success.

First and foremost, climate adaptation measures best practices prioritise ecological integrity. This concept stresses preserving and restoring varied and healthy ecosystems, distinguished by native vegetation, natural habitats, and functional biological processes. By targeting locations with high ecosystem integrity, climate adaptation measures such as NBS interventions can improve biodiversity,

sustain ecosystem services, and minimize the effects of environmental degradation, all of which contribute to landscape and community health and resilience.

Climate adaptation measures and activities should favour areas that promote ecological connectedness, which allows for the flow of species, nutrients, and genetic material across landscapes. This connection improves biodiversity, resilience to environmental change, and ecosystems' capacity to adapt and develop over time. By encouraging connection within and across ecosystems, interventions can improve ecological networks and protect vital habitats, guaranteeing natural systems' long-term sustainability.

Furthermore, resilience is a crucial element influencing climate adaptation measures site selection and design. Climate adaptation interventions should improve ecosystem resilience to climate change, natural disasters, and other disturbances by choosing locations that can withstand present and future environmental stresses. This may include integrating varied habitat types, utilizing natural processes, and using adaptive management measures to improve ecosystems' capacity to endure and recover from shocks. NBS initiatives, for example, will enhance resilience and can ensure the continuous supply of ecosystem functions and services in the face of uncertainty and change.

Climate adaptation best practices stress the value of multifunctionality in site selection and design. NBS interventions should provide numerous advantages on ecological, social, and economic levels (Oen, 2019) by selecting places that sustain various ecosystem services while also meeting societal requirements. By enhancing multifunctionality, NBS interventions can optimize resource utilization, increase cost-effectiveness, and foster community participation and support, thus maximising the positive impact of climate adaptation interventions on both people and nature.

In addition to that, a participative approach is critical for climate adaptation intervention site selection and design. Including stakeholders in the decision-making process ensures that NBS solutions represent a variety of viewpoints and beliefs, resulting in more socially acceptable, equitable, and successful outcomes. Participatory approaches strengthen the legitimacy and sustainability of climate adaptation interventions by encouraging collaboration and ownership among local communities, indigenous peoples, government agencies, NGOs, businesses, and academia, resulting in more resilient landscapes, cities, and communities.

In conclusion, climate adaptation measures best practices and recommendations for site selection and design highlight characteristics such as ecosystem integrity, connectedness, resilience, multifunctionality, and participatory methods. Integrating these concepts into climate adaptation interventions allows practitioners to create solutions that increase ecosystem health and resilience, promote sustainable development, and improve the well-being of communities all over the world.

Integration of multiple benefits, including ecosystem services, social co-benefits, and economic value.

First and foremost, ecosystem services are essential to climate adaptation best practices. Ecosystem services are the advantages that humans gain from nature, such as provisioning services like food, water, and wood, regulating services like climate management and flood control, and cultural services like recreation and spiritual fulfilment. Recognizing and quantifying the value of ecosystem services allows climate adaptation initiatives to demonstrate their impact to human well-being while also supporting decision-making processes that prioritize nature conservation and restoration.

Climate adaptation guidelines underline the significance of social co-benefits in intervention design. Social co-benefits are the positive effects of climate adaptation initiatives on human communities, such as better health and well-being, stronger social cohesiveness, and more access to natural areas. By include social co-benefits in climate adaptation interventions design and implementation, practitioners may ensure that interventions are relevant to local communities' needs and interests, enabling better acceptance and support for nature-based methods.

Economic value is another key factor in climate adaptation best practices. Economic valuation methodologies can aid in quantifying the monetary worth of environmental services and social co-benefits, allowing decision-makers to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of climate adaptation measures and compare them to traditional infrastructure solutions. By proving the economic benefits of climate adaptation, such as lower healthcare expenses, higher property prices, and improved tourism revenue, practitioners may seek investment and finance for nature-based initiatives, therefore creating new prospects for sustainable development.

Climate adaptation guidelines promote a comprehensive strategy to integrate numerous benefits, emphasizing the interdependence of ecological, social, and economic systems. Practitioners can optimize the total effect and value of climate adaptation interventions by creating treatments with synergistic benefits across these dimensions. For example, restoring coastal wetlands not only offers habitat for biodiversity and protects against storm surges, but it also improves recreational possibilities and supports local fisheries, resulting in a win-win situation for both nature and humans.

Additionally, climate adaptation best practices emphasize the importance of participatory decision-making processes that engage stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle. By involving local communities, indigenous peoples, government agencies, NGOs, businesses, and academia in NBS planning, implementation, and monitoring, practitioners can ensure that interventions reflect diverse perspectives and values, leading to more socially equitable and environmentally sustainable outcomes. The value of participatory decision-making procedures that involve stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan is also stressed in the guidelines. Including local communities, indigenous peoples, government agencies, NGOs, businesses, and academia in NBS planning, implementation, and monitoring allows practitioners to ensure that interventions reflect diverse perspectives and values, resulting in more socially equitable and environmentally sustainable outcomes.

In conclusion, climate adaptation best practices and recommendations for integrating diverse benefits prioritize concepts such as ecological services, social co-benefits, and economic value. Practitioners may optimize the total effect and value of climate adaptation measures techniques by using a holistic approach that takes into account the interconnectivity of ecological, social, and economic systems, resulting in more sustainable and resilient landscapes, cities, and communities.

Stakeholder engagement and participatory approaches that foster collaboration, equity, and community ownership.

To begin, inclusive and equitable principles underpin stakeholder participation in climate adaptation activities. This entails actively incorporating a diverse variety of stakeholders, including local communities, indigenous peoples, government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), corporations, and academics, in decision-making processes. By ensuring that varied viewpoints and interests are represented, stakeholders may offer significant ideas, local knowledge, and experience

to the design, implementation, and assessment of climate adaptation initiatives. Furthermore, equitable participation fosters social justice by allowing marginalized people to influence choices that impact their lives and livelihoods.

Collaborative methods of stakeholder involvement are founded on values of openness, accountability, and trust-building. Climate adaptation practitioners try to engage stakeholders in an open and transparent discussion by giving clear information about project objectives, methods, and outcomes. By developing trust and mutual respect, collaborative techniques allow stakeholders to communicate issues, voice ideas, and participate in decision-making in a friendly and constructive setting. This open and inclusive communication generates a sense of ownership and collaborative responsibility for the success of climate adaptation projects, giving them more credibility and efficacy in the eyes of stakeholders. Furthermore, participatory methods for climate adaptation interventions highlight the value of co-designing and co-creating solutions with local communities and stakeholders. Rather than imposing top-down treatments, climate adaptation practitioners collaborate with stakeholders to set goals, define objectives, and devise contextually suitable and culturally sensitive approaches. By embracing local knowledge, traditions, and viewpoints, participatory techniques guarantee that climate adaptation initiatives are adapted to the needs and ambitions of communities, increasing their relevance, acceptability, and long-term sustainability.

Climate adaptation best practices emphasize the need to develop capacity and empower stakeholders to actively engage in decision-making processes. This may include offering training, technical support, and resources to help stakeholders better grasp climate adaptation ideas, methodologies, and tools. By increasing capacity and developing a learning and innovation culture, climate adaptation practitioners enable stakeholders to take ownership of climate adaptation activities, resulting in more effective implementation and long-term management of natural resources.

The unifying themes and ideas that drive climate adaptation best practices and guidelines for stakeholder engagement and participatory techniques emphasize cooperation, equity, and community ownership. By adopting inclusive, transparent, and participatory approaches, climate adaptation practitioners may promote collaborations, build trust, and enable stakeholders to co-create solutions to difficult environmental and social concerns. Climate adaptation projects may have important and long-term results by working together and according to these principles, resulting in more sustainable and resilient landscapes, cities, and communities overall.

Adaptive management and monitoring systems that enable continuous learning, feedback, and adjustment over time.

Adaptive management is a dynamic and iterative approach to decision-making, with strategies altered depending on continual monitoring, assessment, and learning. Climate adaptation best practices emphasize natural systems' inherent ambiguity and complexity, demanding flexible and responsive management techniques that can adapt to changing conditions and new understanding. By incorporating adaptive management concepts into climate adaptation interventions, practitioners can improve their capacity to accomplish desired results while avoiding risks and optimizing benefits for both people and the environment.

Establishing strong monitoring mechanisms that allow stakeholders to track the success and implications of climate adaptation initiatives over time is critical to adaptive management. Monitoring systems should be developed to collect pertinent data on ecological, social, and economic variables, allowing practitioners to track progress, detect trends, and assess the efficacy of climate adaptation

measures. Monitoring systems lay the groundwork for evidence-based decision-making by collecting accurate and timely data, allowing stakeholders to make educated decisions and prioritize actions that maximize the benefits of climate adaptation initiatives. Furthermore, adaptive management and monitoring systems support ongoing learning and feedback loops, allowing stakeholders to fine-tune tactics, enhance results, and create resilience over time. This iterative approach entails assessing monitoring data, identifying lessons learned, and disseminating information and best practices to stakeholders. Adaptive management and monitoring systems enable practitioners to identify emerging challenges, seize opportunities, and adapt climate adaptation interventions to changing circumstances, ensuring their ongoing relevance and effectiveness in meeting evolving environmental and societal needs.

Adaptive management concepts stress stakeholder involvement and participatory decision-making procedures. Practitioners may ensure that climate adaptation interventions represent a wide range of views, values, and interests by including various stakeholders throughout the adaptive management cycle, including local communities, indigenous peoples, government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), corporations, and academics. This inclusive approach strengthens the legitimacy, transparency, and societal acceptability of climate adaptation initiatives, encouraging increased collaboration, ownership, and support among stakeholders.

In conclusion, the unifying themes and ideas underlying climate adaptation best practices and guidelines for adaptive management and monitoring systems stress the need of allowing for continual learning, feedback, and change over time. By incorporating adaptive management concepts into climate adaptation measures and building strong monitoring systems, practitioners may improve their capacity to achieve desired results, increase resilience, and successfully handle complex environmental and social concerns. Stakeholders may exploit the transformational potential of climate adaptation by adopting a collaborative and iterative decision-making strategy to build more sustainable, resilient, and inclusive landscapes, cities, and communities.

Capacity building and knowledge sharing initiatives that empower stakeholders and facilitate cross-sectoral collaboration.

Capacity development activities in the field of climate adaptation stress the necessity of equipping stakeholders with the technical competence and skills required to successfully plan, execute, and monitor climate adaptation interventions. This includes providing training programs, workshops, and instructional materials that are adapted to the individual requirements and capacities of various stakeholders, such as government agencies, local communities, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), corporations, and academics. Climate adaptation efforts may help stakeholders make better decisions, utilize new solutions, and negotiate complicated regulatory and institutional frameworks, resulting in more sustainable and resilient results.

Knowledge sharing efforts are critical to climate adaptation best practices because they enable the interchange of information, experiences, and lessons learned across stakeholders from various sectors and geographic locations. This might include building networks, platforms, and partnerships that promote cooperation and knowledge exchange, such as community practice groups, online forums, and peer-to-peer learning exchanges. Knowledge sharing programs build a culture of learning and innovation, allowing stakeholders to access cutting-edge research, best practices, and practical tools, equipping them to handle growing issues and grasp opportunities in the area of climate adaptation.

Furthermore, capacity building and information exchange programs within the context of climate adaptation highlight the value of inclusion and participatory approaches. These programs should involve a diverse set of stakeholders, including marginalized and underrepresented groups, in decision-making and knowledge-generation activities. By guaranteeing the inclusion of various views, information, and skills, capacity building and knowledge sharing programs may improve the relevance, legitimacy, and efficacy of climate adaptation interventions, resulting in more equitable and sustainable outcomes for all stakeholders. Finally, capacity building and information sharing activities in the framework of climate adaptation highlight the significance of adaptive management and continual learning. Stakeholders should be prepared with the skills and resources required to monitor, assess, and change climate adaptation initiatives in response to growing scientific knowledge, stakeholder feedback, and real-world results. By implementing adaptive management concepts, capacity development and knowledge sharing activities allow stakeholders to increase the efficacy and resilience of climate adaptation interventions over time, guaranteeing their long-term viability and impact in the face of uncertainty and change.

Climate adaptation best practices emphasize the need of multidisciplinary collaboration and partnership-building across sectors and disciplines. Capacity-building and knowledge-sharing projects should promote cross-sectoral collaboration by bringing together stakeholders from environmental conservation, urban planning, water management, agriculture, infrastructure development, and other sectors to solve common concerns holistically. By encouraging cooperation and partnership-building, these projects can help to integrate climate adaptation concepts into wider policy agendas and planning processes, resulting in better coordinated and effective ways to solving environmental and social concerns.

Capacity development and information sharing programs are critical components of climate adaptation best practices because they empower stakeholders and facilitate cross-sectoral collaboration in addressing complex environmental and social concerns efficiently. These initiatives, which embrace principles such as inclusivity, participatory approaches, interdisciplinary collaboration, and adaptive management, enable stakeholders to build capacity, share knowledge, and foster innovation in order to implement sustainable and resilient climate adaptation interventions that benefit both people and nature.

Challenges and Opportunities

Despite significant progress, several challenges persist in the implementation of climate adaptation best practices and guidelines. These include:

- Limited awareness and understanding of climate adaptation concepts and approaches among policymakers, practitioners, and the general public.
- Institutional barriers and regulatory frameworks that may hinder the adoption of modern climate adaptation solutions or favor traditional engineering solutions.
- Funding constraints and resource limitations, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where climate adaptation solutions implementation may require innovative financing mechanisms and partnerships.
- Knowledge gaps and uncertainties regarding the long-term effectiveness, scalability, and replicability of climate adaptation interventions across different contexts and scales.

However, these challenges also present opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and policy reform. By leveraging emerging technologies, interdisciplinary research, and strategic partnerships,

stakeholders can overcome barriers and unlock the full potential of climate adaptation interventions to address global sustainability challenges.

Future Directions

Looking ahead, future research and action in the field of climate adaptation best practices and guidelines should focus on:

- Advancing the evidence base through rigorous monitoring, evaluation, and knowledge exchange.
- Promoting cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary approaches that integrate climate adaptation into broader policy agendas, such as climate adaptation, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable development.
- Strengthening capacity building efforts to empower local communities, government agencies, and other stakeholders to implement climate adaptation solutions effectively and equitably.
- Advocating for supportive policies, incentives, and regulatory frameworks that incentivize the adoption of climate adaptation solutions and remove barriers to implementation.

In conclusion, the current state of best practices and guidelines for climate adaptation solutions reflects a dynamic and evolving field characterized by innovation, collaboration, and a growing recognition of the importance of nature in addressing complex sustainability challenges. By building on existing knowledge, fostering partnerships, and embracing adaptive management approaches, stakeholders can accelerate the transition towards a more resilient, equitable, and nature-positive future.

3. Avoid damages framework in TransformAr

Overall concept and method

In the context of the TransformAr project, the concept of Damages and Avoid Damages from climate change is developed and defined based on the current literature. As such, **damages** from climate change encompass a broad range of adverse impacts that are not adequately mitigated or adapted to, while **avoided damages** represent the benefits of effective mitigation and adaptation efforts, preventing potential future impacts. In D3.4 the methodology for assessing damages and calculating avoided damages was presented and follows two approaches. The **High Data Availability - KPI-Based Approach** quantifies climate hazards and their impacts using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across five categories: Physical, Social, Environmental, Health, and Economic. These KPIs are scaled and weighted based on expert input to estimate direct, indirect, and people-related damages, with the effectiveness of implemented solutions assessed by comparing KPIs before and after adaptation measures. In contrast, **the Sparse Data – High-Level Approach** is designed for cases with limited data availability and follows the IPCC risk framework, estimating damages based on hazard exposure and vulnerability. This approach incorporates global temperature shocks and economic modeling to determine direct and indirect damages.

In both approaches, the avoided damages are then calculated by comparing two scenarios: the Baseline (Bs), which represents the current situation with or without solutions, and Climate Change (CC), which represents future conditions under different climate scenarios with and without solutions. The difference in damages between these states defines avoided damages, which are categorized into Short-term, representing immediate benefits from adaptation measures, and Long-term, projecting benefits for future climate scenarios. These methodologies provide a structured approach to evaluating climate adaptation strategies and their effectiveness in mitigating risks.

Table 3.1 Formulas to assess Avoided Damages from Climate Changes.

	Baseline (now)	Future (CC)
No Solution implementation	$D_{Bs}^{nS} = f(\text{direct}, \text{indirect}, \text{people})$	$D_{CC}^{nS} = f(\text{direct}, \text{indirect}, \text{people})$
With Solution implementation	$D_{Bs}^S = g(\text{direct}, \text{indirect}, \text{people})$	$D_{CC}^S = g(\text{direct}, \text{indirect}, \text{people})$
Avoided damages	$AD_{Bs} = \frac{D_{Bs}^{nS} - D_{Bs}^S}{D_{Bs}^{nS}}$	$AD_{CC} = \frac{D_{Bs}^{nS} - D_{CC}^S}{D_{Bs}^{nS}}$
<i>nS: no Solution S: Solutions Bs: Baseline CC: Climate Change D: Damages AD: Avoided Damages</i>		

4. Avoided damages assessment: High Data Availability – KPI Based

The case study of Municipality of Egaleo (MOE)

Overview

The municipality of Egaleo (MOE), Greece (37.9924° N, 23.6781° E) is situated at the west region of the urban planning complex of the region of Attica and has been built at both sides of the ancient road «Iera Odos». It is approximately 4km away from Athens. The borders of Egaleo can be seen in Figure 2 below. The population of the city is around 120.000. The city is exposed to heat waves (expected to increase with CC), extreme precipitations, thunderstorms, and flooding events.

MOE, being part of the Western Region of Attika in Greece, belongs to the wider Mediterranean biogeographical region. As thoroughly assessed earlier on, MOE is at great risk of drought and wildfires fires of the «Baroutadiko Grove». Furthermore, heatwaves also pose a dire heat stress danger to elder citizens, vulnerable groups and to households that cannot afford adequate cooling, which also stresses the issue of energy demands of cooling. Among the major natural risks that are threatening Egaleo are fires caused by the severe temperatures and the dryness of the vegetation during summertime.

Another potential natural risk for Egaleo is flooding from urban flash floods, which is due to the insufficient flood risk management systems. Egaleo is located near Kifissos river, which has a high risk of flooding during mid-autumn-winter session, causing massive damage to the area. Severe floods with peoples deaths occurred in 1934 in 1954 and in 1997 (Egaleo Book, 2023)

There has been a series of wildfires roaming throughout summertime in Greece. MOE has not experienced a direct episode of fire in Baroutadiko Grove, although each summer temperatures have been reaching up to 45°C, putting the municipality in an alarming state.

The issues that Egaleo is facing, increasing the territory's vulnerability from a climate perspective, including:

- Slow population growth rate, high unemployment rate and the prevalence of vulnerable groups (migrants, offenders). These groups often lack the resources to protect themselves against severe climate effects and the slower economic growth of MOE makes it difficult with keeping up with their support.
- Infrastructures, mostly the inefficient street planning, the lack of public spaces and parking lots. That leads to surplus people activity in public spaces and increased traffic volume that can cause amplified harm to the environment of the area.
- Direct environmental issues caused by the industrial activity in Eleonas and Yula areas.
- Increasing temperature in MOE during summertime is evidence for its citizens to realize the existence and impact that climate change yields. This could urge them to become more aware about their living habits and start changing their lifestyle to an eco-friendlier one (e.g. start using public transportation more, reduce in-house electricity usage, not litter the streets).

The methodology was successfully applied to MOE for the climate hazard of heatwave. A series of meetings between NCSRD and MOE, alongside bilateral meetings with local stakeholders and experts of MOE's infrastructures and services, were performed. The information compiled accomplished by following the steps below:

- Define the climate problem
- Decide the relevant KPIs
- Quantification of KPIs (expert opinion, models, WP2 data) for 3 cases

- Current status (Baseline)
- Future scenario RCP4.5
- Future scenario RCP8.5
- Assess the importance of each KPI
- Present and define the added value of TransformAr solutions
- Quantification of KPIs (expert opinion, models, WP2 data) having in mind the solution implementation

In Table 4.1 the list of KPIs chosen and quantified for MOE are presented.

Table 4.1 KPIs list used by MOE related to climate hazard and solution

KPI Definition	Hazard	Solution	People	Indirect	Direct
Production-based CO2 intensity is calculated as CO2 emissions per capita (tonnes/person).	Heat waves	CIH		x	
Ranking of cities/countries based on annual average PM2.5 concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Heatwaves	SCS			
Variation of annual total carbon dioxide equivalent emissions from energy production, transportation and industry.	Heatwaves	SCS		x	
Perceptions about threats through climate change and environmental catastrophes and how likely they are or will be prevented	Heatwaves	CAE / AWAR	x		
Percentage of the labour force unemployed (working-age residents without work divided by total labour force)	Heatwaves	AWAR, DSI		x	
Percentage of population with access to improved sanitation facilities/ People using safely managed sanitation services	Heatwaves	DSI	x		x
Access to electricity, urban	Heatwaves	DSI		x	x

A person's actual exposure to environmental hazards, such as noise or pollution.	Heatwaves	CAE/SCS	x	x	x
Data on safety and risk collected in the World Risk Poll from over 125,000 people in 121 countries. The Resilience Index is an average of 4 domains: Individual, Household, Community, Society.	Heatwaves	CAE	x	x	x
Perceptions about threats through climate change and environmental catastrophes and how likely they are or will be prevented	Heatwaves	CAE / AWAR	x	x	
The Global Climate Risk Index shows the level of exposure and vulnerability to extreme weather events	Heatwaves	DSI	x	x	x
The mortality rate is calculated by dividing the number of total deaths by the population size for a defined population or geographical area over a specified period. An indicator that can help measure a person's health in a community. It is a measure that affects the population	Heatwaves	DSI	x		
Health impacts of air pollution: air pollutants and greenhouse gases	Heatwaves	DSI	x	x	
The indicator Healthy Life Years (HLY) at birth measures the number of years that a person at birth is still expected to live in a healthy condition. HLY is a health expectancy indicator which combines information on mortality and morbidity. The data required are the age-specific prevalence (proportions) of the population in healthy and unhealthy conditions and age-specific mortality information. A healthy condition is defined by the absence of limitations in functioning/disability.	Heatwaves	DSI	x		

Damage assessment

Following the workflow described in the previous sections, the damages were assessed based on the chosen KPIs. The values were calculated with the help of models, WP2 data, online databases and national reports for the area of Attica. In many occasions, the information collected was needed to be downscaled for the MOE area. The latter was achieved by identifying scaling factors relevant to MOE by utilizing population density, industrial activity, local environmental conditions, and socio-economic data. In addition, interpolation methods (e.g. linear scaling) were utilized to adjust the regional data to the local context. Wherever it was possible the downscaled values were cross-checked with any available local data. The scaled (see Section 3) values are illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Radar plot of the damages assessment of MOE for the case of heatwave for Current status (Baseline), the solution effectiveness and two damage assessments for future climate scenarios (RCP4.5, RCP8.5)

It is found that the mortality rate is high compared to other countries¹ and the problem becomes bigger in the future for scenario RCP8.5, with the exposure to environmental hazards and contribution to climate change driver (CO₂) being the most important areas of damages for MOE.

In the following Tables 4.2, Table 4.3 and Table 4.4 the quantification of the damages categories (Direct, Indirect, People) for the current status (baseline) and the climate scenarios under study. In addition, the information on each solution and damage importance is presented as decided by the MOE demonstrator.

¹ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/death-rate-by-country>

Table 4.2 Quantifications of Direct KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – no Solution (nS)

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	RCP4.5	RCP8.5	Importance(a_n)
Percentage of population with access to improved sanitation facilities/ People using safely managed sanitation services ²	99%	97%	94%	5
Access to electricity, urban ³	100%	100%	98%	5
The Global Climate Risk Index shows the level of exposure and vulnerability to extreme weather events (Risk factor 0-4) ⁴	1	2	2	3

Table 4.3 Quantifications of Indirect KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – no Solution (nS)

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	RCP4.5	RCP8.5	Importance (a_n)
Production-based CO ₂ intensity is calculated as CO ₂ emissions per capita (tonnes/person). ⁵	5.9	5.5	7.2	3

Table 4.3 Quantifications of People KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – no Solution (nS)

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	RCP4.5	RCP8.5	Importance(a_n)
A person's actual exposure to environmental hazards, such as noise or pollution. ⁸	37%	42%	52%	4
Perceptions about threats through climate change and environmental catastrophes and how likely they are or will be prevented ¹²	67%	72%	82%	3

² <https://tradingeconomics.com>

³ International Energy Agency (IEA)

⁴ World bank

⁵ European Environment Agency (EEA)

The mortality rate (per 1,000 people) ⁶	12	12.3	14.5	5
Health impacts of air pollution: air pollutants and greenhouse gases ¹³	34%	37%	42%	4
Healthy Life Years (HLY) (Measures the number of years that a person at birth is still expected to live in a healthy condition.) ⁷	66.6	64.5	63.3	3

Solution assessment

Following the same process and data sources (models, WP2, expert opinion) the effectiveness of the solution was estimated. In the current context it is presented as the change of the KPI for the better (less damage). The latter is essential to be aligned with the previous section and used in the avoided damages assessment. The table 4.7, Table 4.8 and Table 4.9 present the changes to the KPIs after the solution applied.

Table 4.7 Quantifications of Direct KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – Solution (S)

KPI Definition	Solution	Solution (S)
Percentage of population with access to improved sanitation facilities/ People using safely managed sanitation services	DSI	99%
Access to electricity, urban	DSI	100%
The Global Climate Risk Index shows the level of exposure and vulnerability to extreme weather events	DSI	1

Table 4.8 Quantifications of Indirect KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – Solution (S)

KPI Definition	Solution	Solution Baseline (S)
----------------	----------	-----------------------

⁶ Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT)

⁷ Eurostat Health Statistics

Production-based CO2 intensity is calculated as CO2 emissions per capita (tonnes/person).	CIH	5.1
---	-----	-----

Table 4.9 Quantifications of People KPIs for MOE for the case of heatwave – Solution (S)

KPI Definition	Solution	Solution Baseline (S)
A person's actual exposure to environmental hazards, such as noise or pollution.	CAE/SCS	37%
Perceptions about threats through climate change and environmental catastrophes and how likely they are or will be prevented	CAE / AWAR	62%
The mortality rate is calculated by dividing the number of total deaths by the population size for a defined population or geographical area over a specified period. An indicator that can help measure a person's health in a community. It is a measure that affects the population	DSI	11
Health impacts of air pollution: air pollutants and greenhouse gases	DSI	32%
The indicator Healthy Life Years (HLY) at birth measures the number of years that a person at birth is still expected to live in a healthy condition. HLY is a health expectancy indicator which combines information on mortality and morbidity. The data required are the population's age-specific prevalence (proportions) in healthy and unhealthy conditions and age-specific mortality information. The absence of limitations in functioning/disability defines a healthy condition.	DSI	67.8

Avoided damages assessment

Following the methodology presented in Section 3, the analysis of damages and solution effectiveness are combined to assess the avoided damages for the MOE case under the climate hazard of heatwave. Table 4.13 and Table 4.14 present the scaled valued (0-1) in percentage format for the baseline and the two climate scenarios.

Table 4.13 refers to the total avoided damages for MOE for the case of heatwave, whereas the added value of the solutions implementation becomes higher from now to the future. The analysis yields long-term avoided damages between –35.8 to –26% with short-term values –11%.

Table 4.13 Total avoided damages for MOE for the case of heatwave

Total avoided damages	Baseline (now)	RCP4.5	RCP8.5
No Solution implementation	5.4%	6.5%	7.5%

With Solution implementation	4.8%		
Avoided damages	-11.0%	-26.0%	-35.8%

Figure 4.2 Bar plot of the avoided damages assessment per category (Direct, Indirect, People) for MOE for the case of heatwave

Table 4.14 presents the avoided damages broken down to the three categories of Direct, Indirect and People. The direct avoided damages are higher compared to the other two categories with Indirect and People having values similar to the overall avoided damages. Based on that, MOE can benefit a lot even for short-term avoided damages by implementing TransformAr solution and more, thus, addressing the damage areas depicted in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.2 illustrates the avoided damaged categories for all cases, where the direct avoided damages importance is evident.

Table 4.14 Assessment of avoided damages per category (Direct, Indirect, People) for MOE for the case of heatwave

Direct	Baseline (now)	RCP4.5	RCP8.5
No Solution implementation	2.5%	3.9%	4.7%
With Solution implementation	2.0%		
Avoided damages	-20.2%	-48.9%	-57.3%
Indirect			
No Solution implementation	6.3%	7.4%	8.7%

With Solution implementation	5.6%		
Avoided damages	-8.6%	-20.0%	-29.0%
People			
No Solution implementation	6.7%	7.9%	9.1%
With Solution implementation	6.0%		
Avoided damages	-10.6%	-23.3%	-33.7%

The case study of Gjøvik

Overview

Gjøvik is a municipality located in Innlandet County, southeastern Norway, along the western shore of Lake Mjøsa, the country’s largest lake, approximately 120 kilometers north of Oslo. With a population of approximately 30,000 residents, Gjøvik serves as a regional hub for higher education, public services, and technology, hosting the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) campus, which enhances its capacity for knowledge and innovation. The municipality experiences a humid continental climate characterized by cold, snowy winters, mild to warm summers, and relatively consistent precipitation throughout the year.

In recent years, Gjøvik has become increasingly susceptible to climate-related risks, particularly owing to the heightened frequency and intensity of rainfall, extreme weather events, and both urban and waterway flooding. These developments have exerted additional pressure on existing infrastructure, especially the sanitation and drainage systems. To mitigate these challenges, the municipality has formulated a Climate Plan that sets forth strategic objectives for reducing the volumes of stormwater and meltwater entering the city's drainage and sanitation networks. Complementarily, the Plan for Water and Sanitation emphasizes the need to upgrade existing water infrastructure to meet future demands, particularly focusing on enhancing the municipality's capacity to filter and remove contaminants from surface runoff. Collectively, these measures constitute a targeted and proactive approach to climate adaptation, aimed at bolstering the resilience of Gjøvik's infrastructure and safeguarding environmental and public health in the context of a changing climate.

Building on Gjøvik’s municipal climate planning and water management strategies, the TransformAR project has implemented a range of solutions to enhance local resilience to water-related climate risks. These include the deployment of advanced stormwater monitoring systems for real-time data collection to support predictive flood management and pollution control; the installation of a Smart Weather Station to provide high-resolution, localized climate data for evidence-based policy decisions; and the use of decentralized biofiltration areas designed to intercept and treat urban runoff before it enters sanitation networks. Additionally, nature-based solutions addressing nutrient pollution and flood retention, such as green swales and retention basins, have been developed to reduce pollutant loads and moderate peak flows.

Through these measures, Gjøvik progresses from strategic planning to practical implementation, enhancing its adaptive capacity, mitigating urban and waterway flooding, and improving the ecological quality of its drainage systems under projected climate scenarios.

Table 4.15 KPIs list used by Gjøvik region related to climate hazard and solution

KPI Definition	Hazard	Solution	Indirect	Direct
Number of reported incidents (per year)	Flooding	SWMM / URB		X
Damages paid (1000 NOK) (per year)	Flooding	SWMM / URB		X
Number of water damages reported due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)	Flooding	SWMM / URB		X
Damages paid (1000 NOK) due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)	Flooding	SWMM / URB		X
Investment for damage reduction in buildings/houses (euros per household)	Flooding	CEI	X	
Investment for runoff reduction and pollution (euros per household)	Water quality	CEI	X	

Damage assessment

Following the workflow outlined earlier, damages were assessed using chosen KPIs. These values were derived from models, WP2 data, online sources, and national reports pertaining to the Innlandet County. The gathered data had to be downscaled for local accuracy. This involved applying relevant scaling factors for Gjøvik, based on municipal coverage (percentage of the total county), industrial activity, environmental conditions, and socio-economic data. Interpolation methods, such as linear scaling, were also used to tailor regional data to the local context. The resulting scaled values are presented in Figure 4.3a and Figure 4.3b below, for the two future scenarios.

Figure 4.3 Radar plot of the damages assessment of Gjøvik for the case of flooding for Current status (Baseline), the solution effectiveness and two damage assessments for near future climate scenarios (SSP1.26, SSP3.7, and SSP5.85)

Figure 4.4 Radar plot of the damages assessment of Gjøvik for the case of flooding for Current status (Baseline), the solution effectiveness and two damage assessments for far future climate scenarios (SSP1.26, SSP3.7, and SSP5.85)

In the following Tables 4.16a&b and 4.17a&b, the quantification of damage categories (Direct, Indirect) for the current state (baseline) and the SSP climate scenarios under study for the two future periods is presented. Additionally, information on each solution and damage significance is provided as determined by the Gjøvik replicator. The absence of a People's category is due to data unavailability for such KPIs, given that Gjøvik is a replicating region.

Table 4.16a Quantifications of Direct KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – no Solution (nS) - Near Future (NF) 2040 – 2070

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85	Importance(a_n)
Number of average reported incidents (per year)	4.0836	4.206108	4.246944	4.28778	4
Damages paid (1000 NOK) (per year)	692.1456	712.909968	719.831424	726.75288	5
Number of water damages reported due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)	428.0646	440.906538	445.187184	449.46783	3
Damages paid (1000 NOK) due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)	16789.3524	17293.033	17460.9265	17628.82	4

Table 4.16b Quantifications of Direct KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – no Solution (nS) – Far Future (FF) 2070 - 2100

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85	Importance(a_n)
Number of average reported incidents (per year)	4.0836	4.165272	4.369452	4.49196	4
Damages paid (1000 NOK) (per year)	692.1456	705.988512	740.595792	761.36016	5
Number of water damages reported due to water entering properties above ground or	428.0646	436.625892	458.029122	470.87106	3

below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)					
Damages paid (1000 NOK) due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)	16789.3524	17125.1394	17964.6071	18468.2876	4

Table 4.17a Quantifications of Indirect KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – no Solution (nS) - based on the highest performance solutions (75% reduction) - Near Future (NF) 2040 – 2070

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85	Importance(a_n)
Investment for damage reduction in buildings/houses (euros per household)	2130	2193.9	2215.2	2236.5	3
Investment for runoff reduction and pollution (euros per household)	3050	3141.5	3172	3202.5	2

Table 4.17b Quantifications of Indirect KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – no Solution (nS) - based on the highest performance solutions (75% reduction) – Far Future (FF) 2070 - 2100

KPI Definition	Baseline (Bs)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85	Importance(a_n)
Investment for damage reduction in buildings/houses (euros per household)	2130	2172.6	2279.1	2343	3
Investment for runoff reduction and pollution (euros per household)	3050	3111	3263.5	3355	2

Solution assessment

Following the same process and data sources as in the case of MOE, the effectiveness of the solutions for the Gjøvik area was estimated. In the current context, it is presented as an improvement in the KPI (reduction in damage). The latter is essential to be aligned with the previous section and used in the avoided damages assessment. Tables 4.19 and 4.20 show the changes to the KPIs after the solution was implemented.

Table 4.19 Quantifications of Direct KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – Solution (S)

KPI Definition	Solution	Solution (S)
Number of average reported incidents (per year)	SWMM / URB	1
Damages paid (1000 NOK) (per year)		173
Number of water damages reported due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)		107
Damages paid (1000 NOK) due to water entering properties above ground or below ground (rain, meltwater, ground water)		4197

Table 4.20 Quantifications of Indirect KPIs for Gjøvik region for the case of flooding events – Solution (S)

KPI Definition	Solution	Solution (S)
Investment for damage reduction in buildings/houses (euros per household)	CEI	838
Investment for runoff reduction and pollution (euros per household)		1270

Avoided damages

Near Future (NF) scenarios

Following the methodology, the analysis of damages and solution effectiveness are integrated to evaluate the avoided damages for the Gjøvik replicator under flooding climate hazards. Tables 4.21 and 4.22 show the scaled values (0-1) in percentage format for both the baseline and the three climate scenarios for the period 2040-2070.

Gjøvik's total avoided damages for flooding, with the benefits of solution implementation increasing over time. The analysis shows long-term avoided damages ranging from –48.1% to –47.1%, while short-term avoided damages are –23.6%.

Table 4.21 Total avoided damages for Gjøvik for the case of floods.

Total avoided damages	Baseline (now)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85
No Solution implementation	7.3%	10.5%	10.6%	10.7%
With Solution implementation	5.6%			
Avoided damages	-23.6%	-47.1%	-47.6%	-48.1%

Figure 4.5 Bar plot of the avoided damages assessment per category (Direct, Indirect) for Gjøvik for the case of flooding.

Table 4.22 shows the avoided damages divided into two categories: Direct and Indirect. The avoided damages for Indirect are higher than for Direct because citizens are willing to pay for the most effective adaptation measures. The effectiveness in preventing damages improves for the 3 SSP scenarios as risk increases. On the contrary, the effectiveness of the solutions (SWMM and URB) linked to the Direct damages increases dramatically in all near-future scenarios by at least 28.7%.

Table 4.22 Assessment of avoided damages per category (Direct, Indirect) for Gjøvik for the case of flooding.

Direct	Baseline (now)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85
No Solution implementation	8.0%	12.2%	12.4%	12.5%
With Solution implementation	6.7%			
Avoided damages	-16.6%	-45.3%	-45.8%	-46.3%
Indirect	Baseline (now)	SSP 1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP 5.85
No Solution implementation	5.0%	5.1%	5.2%	5.2%
With Solution implementation	2.0%			
Avoided damages	-59.5%	-60.7%	-61.1%	-61.5%

Far Future (FF) scenarios

The methodology combines damage analysis and solution effectiveness to assess the avoided damages for the Gjøvik replicator under flooding climate hazards. Tables 4.23 and 4.24 display scaled values (0-1) as percentages for both the baseline case and three climate scenarios from 2070 to 2100.

Gjøvik's total avoided damages from flooding increase over time as the benefits of the solution are realised. The analysis indicates long-term avoided damages ranging from -50.4% to -46.6%, while short-term avoided damages remain -23.6%, as in the case for the near future scenarios.

Table 4.23 Total avoided damages for Gjøvik for the case of floods.

Total avoided damages	Baseline (now)	SSP1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP5.85
No Solution implementation	7.3%	10.4%	11.0%	11.3%
With Solution implementation	5.6%			
Avoided damages	-23.6%	-46.6%	-49.1%	-50.4%

Figure 4.6 Bar plot of the avoided damages assessment per category (Direct, Indirect) for Gjøvik for the case of flooding.

Table 4.28 presents the avoided damages categorised into Direct and Indirect. The avoided damages are greater for Indirect because citizens are willing to pay more for the most effective adaptation measures. The effectiveness of damage prevention improves for the 3 SSP scenarios as risk levels rise. Conversely, the solutions associated with Direct damages (SWMM and URB) show a significant increase in effectiveness across all far-future scenarios, with improvements of at least 28.1%.

Regardless of the scenarios and future periods, the damages prevented by the solutions implemented in the Gjøvik area demonstrate increased effectiveness and consequently a reduction in damages due to flooding events.

Table 4.24 Assessment of avoided damages per category (Direct, Indirect) for Gjøvik for the case of flooding.

Direct	Short-term	SSP1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP5.85
No Solution implementation	8.0%	12.1%	12.7%	13.1%
With Solution implementation	6.7%			
Avoided damages	-16.6%	-44.7%	-47.3%	-48.8%
Indirect	Baseline (now)	SSP1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP5.85

No Solution implementation	5.0%	5.1%	5.3%	5.5%
With Solution implementation	2.0%			
Avoided damages	-59.5%	-60.3%	-62.2%	-63.2%

5. Avoided damages assessment: Sparse Data – High-Level Approach

The case study of West Country region

Climate change context

The provided charts display projections for three key drought-related variables in the West Country, UK, derived from TransformAR outputs of WP2⁸, mean air temperature, number of hot days, and continuous dry days under two distinct climate scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (low emissions, sustainability, warming stabilizes ~1.8°C by 2100) and SSP5-8.5 (high emissions, fossil-fuel intensive, warming ~4.4°C by 2100).

Mean Air Temperature for SSP1-2.6

Mean Air Temperature for SSP5-8.5

Number of Hot Days for SSP1-2.6

Number of Hot Days for SSP5-8.5

⁸ https://kfo.pik-potsdam.de/eur/index.html?language_id=en

Figure 5.1 Climate conditions for the West Country region

The variables are relevant to the main extreme event under study for the region, droughts. Under higher temperatures more evapotranspiration occurs leading to soil moisture loss. The number of Hot Days is an indicator of increased drought stress and continuous dry days indicates more frequent and severe drought events.

In case of Mean Air Temperature and SSP1-2.6, the temperatures rise moderately, followed by a plateau in mid-century. The increase is contained, reflecting strong mitigation. On the other hand, in SSP5-8.5, a steep, continuous rise until 2085 indicates much greater warming and drought risk. The Number of Hot Days is increase until mid-century in case of SSP1-2.6, and then stabilize or slightly decline. For the SSP5-8.5, the hot days rise sharply showing a dramatic increase that suggests frequent extreme heat events. The Continuous Dry Days in SSP1-2.6 are increasing slightly and then plateau, indicating limited additional drought risk in a low-emissions world, whereas, in SSP5-8.5 are steadily increasing, pointing to more frequent and severe droughts.

Table 5.1 Summarization of climate context for West Country region

Variable	SSP1-2.6 (Sustainability)	SSP5-8.5 (Fossil-fuel intensive)
Mean Air Temperature	Moderate rise, then plateau	Continuous, steep rise
Number of Hot Days	Increases, then stabilizes	Sharp, ongoing increase
Continuous Dry Days	Slight increase, then plateau	Steady, significant increase

The implications for Drought Risk in the UK can be summed according to each climate scenario differently. The Low-Emissions Pathway (SSP1-2.6) projects a drought-related extremes (temperature, hot days, dry spells) modest increase and then a stabilization. This potentially means that the adaptation is more manageable, and the risk of unprecedented droughts is limited. In case of High-Emissions Pathway (SSP5-8.5), all drought-related extremes rise sharply, especially after mid-century, with the frequency and severity of droughts increase substantially, with much higher uncertainty and risk of extreme events. It is noted that for the current analysis, data modelling and projection were provided from WP2 as input.

Historic extreme events – Drought ^{9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18}

The West Country of the United Kingdom, encompassing South West England, has faced escalating drought-related challenges in recent years, with significant environmental, economic, and social repercussions. The available data on damages from extreme drought events in the region, drawing on hydrological records, governmental assessments, and utility company disclosures. Key findings reveal that the 2022 drought, one of the most severe in nearly a century, exposed critical vulnerabilities in water resource management, infrastructure resilience, and agricultural preparedness.

The 2022 drought was characterized by a 12-month rainfall deficit ranking among the driest periods since 1891. Combined with the highest observed temperatures since 1884, evaporation rates surged, amplifying soil moisture deficits and reducing effective precipitation-the actual water available to replenish aquifers and reservoirs-by up to 40%. These conditions created a "compound drought," where heat and aridity synergistically exacerbated water scarcity. The latter had environmental damages and ecological strain to the region, alongside agricultural and economic consequences, such as crop losses and irrigation demands and water costs and utility pressures. The table below depicts the literature review results that will be used to establish a baseline for the damages in the current sparse availability analysis.

Table 5.2 Quantification of impacts of historic extreme events for West Country region

	Description / Example Damages	Quantitative Data (if available)	Reference / Source
Water Supply	Reservoirs (e.g., Colliford, Roadford) fell to 30€ - 40% capacity; emergency drought permits issued; hosepipe bans for first time in 26 years	Water bills in region: £491/year (highest in UK); 23% bill increase projected over 5 years	https://www.southwestwater.co.uk/environment/water-resources/drought-plan

⁹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/all-of-england-s-south-west-region-now-in-drought>

¹⁰ <https://smartwatermagazine.com/news/govuk/all-englands-south-west-region-now-drought>

¹¹ https://www.southwestwater.co.uk/siteassets/documents/about-us/wrmp/sww_draft_wrmp24_chapter_1_app_1_insights_from_2022_drought.pdf

¹² https://consult.environment-agency.gov.uk/environment-and-business/drought-how-it-is-managed-in-england/supporting_documents/Drought_How_it_is_managed_in_England.pdf

<https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/25/77/2025/>

¹³ <https://www.southwestwater.co.uk/environment/water-resources/drought-plan>

¹⁴ <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/crmkn7rjv7zo>

¹⁵ <https://agriculture.vic.gov.au/farm-management/dry-seasons-and-drought-support/south-west-drought-support-package>

¹⁶ <https://www.savemoneycutcarbon.com/learn-save/why-the-south-west-has-the-highest-water-costs-and-what-to-do-about-it/>

¹⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-devon-67964356>

¹⁸ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/pesetaiv_task_7_drought_final_report.pdf

Agriculture	Crop yield reductions (maize, potatoes down 15€ - 25%); early irrigation withdrawals; increased feed costs for livestock	No region-specific monetary figure; UK-wide drought cost estimated at £600 million/year average	https://www.ciwem.org/assets/pdf/Policy/Policy%20Position%20Statement/Drought%20PPS%20CIWEM%20May%202025.pdf
Environmental	Exceptionally low river flows; fish rescues; algal blooms; habitat loss for salmon, trout, and other species	No direct monetary value; multiple rivers at record-low flows	https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/crmkn7rjv7zo
Utility/Infrastructure	Emergency water trucking; accelerated infrastructure spending (desalination, new sources)	£36 million desalination plant	https://www.southwestwater.co.uk/environment/water-resources/drought-plan
Tourism/Business	Disrupted water supply to hotels, campsites, golf courses; landscaping restrictions	Not quantified, but significant local economic impact reported	https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/crmkn7rjv7zo

Avoided damages assessment

Input data

In order to implement the sparse data availability approach a compilation of different type of data was compiled from different sources. Climate information were provided via WP2, D5.2 provided the solution effectiveness and historic damages information were gather via online resources. It is noted that climate information plots and analysis can be found in ANNEX II.

Table 5.3 Input data for historic period for West Country region

	Variable	Value	Source
Historical climate data	Average annual extreme events	0.2	WP2
	Intensity index (1-5 scale)	min=6, max=70, avg=35	WP2
	Area population	~5.7M (not used as no downscaled was performed)	Deliverables / Online sources

	Total area size [km ²]	~24,386.00 (not used as no downscaled was performed)	Deliverables / Online sources
	Climate risk index (0-1 scale)	0.2	WP2

Table 5.4 Input data for climate projections SSP126 for West Country region

Low emissions future climate data	Variable	Value (2071-2100 SSP126)	Source
	Projected annual events	0.6	WP2
	Projected Intensity stats	min=20, max=80, avg=45	WP2
	Population change factor	0.15	WP2

Table 5.5 Input data for climate projections SSP585 for West Country region

High emissions future climate data	Variable	Value (2071-2100 SSP585)	Source
	Projected annual events	1	WP2
	Projected Intensity index stats	min=50, max=130, avg=80	WP2
	Population change factor	0.18	WP2

Table 5.6 Input data for solution efficiency and damage assessment for West Country region

	Solution efficiency		Damage Factor [unit(e.g. €)/event/intensity unit]	
	Value	Source	Value	Source
Direct	-	D5.2 DB	Utility/Infrastructure = £36 million desalination plant	D3.5 (previous section)
Indirect	Economic_avg(RSP)=3.05 Enviromental_ avg(RSP)=3.54	D5.2 DB	Agri = £600 million/year average	D3.5 (previous section)
People	Socia_avg(RSP)=4.52	D5.2 DB	-	D3.5 (previous section)

Assessment

To perform the analysis and assess the avoided damages, the algorithm developed and described in D3.4 and published in ZENODO <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15324264> was used. The data type utilised in order to perform the assessment are shown above, and directly affect the type of results.

The solutions are not relevant with direct damages and the people category has not history damage data reference. the total damages can be shown

Table 5.7 Assessment results for West Country region

Total avoided damages	Baseline (now)	SSP2-1.6	SSP5-8.5
No Solution implementation	4,319,040£	18,711,792£	34,069,200£
With Solution implementation	3,502,327£	15,175,060£	27,631,010£
Avoided damages	820,000£	3,540,000£	6,440,000£

In case of West Country region, the avoided damages assessment with the sparse data approach yields 0.8M to 6.4M euros depending on the climate scenario. All damages derived from the indirect category as no data for damages were acquired for people category and no solution relevant to direct damages was applied. It is noted that the table above is provide the damages values alongside the avoided damages, whereas, the Figure below illustrated the avoided damages only.

Figure 5.2 Bar plot of avoided damages for the case of West Country region

The case study of City of Lappeenranta

Climate change context

The provided charts illustrate projections for two key flood-related variables in Lappeenranta: annual precipitation (top row) and climatic water balance (bottom row). Each variable is shown under two climate scenarios, SSP1-2.6 (sustainability/low emissions, left) and SSP5-8.5 (fossil-fuel intensive/high emissions, right), with the time horizon extending to 2100. The analysis focuses on how these variables that influence flood risk. The annual precipitation increase will increase flood potential, whereas, climatic water balance if positive (precipitation > evapotranspiration) increases runoff and flood risk.

Annual precipitation for SSP1-2.6

Annual precipitation for SSP5-8.5

Climatic Water Balance for SSP1-2.6

Climatic Water Balance for SSP5-8.5

Figure 5.3 Climate conditions for City of Lappeenranta

In case of annual precipitation, both scenarios project a relatively stable situation across all future periods, with only minor variations between scenarios. If we take into account the uncertainty (error bars), there is some variability, but no strong upward or downward trend is observed. The stable precipitation suggests that, by itself, rainfall volume may not significantly increase flood risk, but other factors (e.g., intensity, seasonality) that are not available in TransformAr Climate Impacts in Europe database, may affect the flood risk. In case of Climatic Water Balance, the SSP1-2.6 show a moderate downward trend, but remain well above zero, indicating that precipitation continues to exceed evapotranspiration, whereas, in SSP5-8.5, the decline is much steeper approaching zero by the end of

the century. A decline in climatic water balance suggests reduced surplus water available for runoff, potentially lowering flood risk from excess precipitation. However, the balance remains positive for most of the period, so flood potential persists, especially during extreme events. It is noted that for the current analysis, data modelling and projection were provided from WP2 as input.

The implications for Flood Risk in Lappeenranta, remains relatively stable, with precipitation and water balance showing only modest changes for the case of SSP1-2.6 (Sustainability). In addition continued positive water balance means that the region will still experience periods with excess water, maintaining some flood risk. On the other hand, in SSP5-8.5 (High Emissions), while annual precipitation does not increase, the climatic water balance declines sharply, indicating less surplus water for potential flooding.

Table 5.8 Summarization of climate context for city of Lappeenranta

Variable	SSP1-2.6 (Sustainability)	SSP5-8.5 (Fossil-fuel intensive)
Annual Precipitation	Stable, slight variation	Stable, slight variation
Climatic Water Balance	Moderate decline, remains positive	Steep decline, approaches zero at low percentiles

Historic extreme events – Floods ^{19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26}

Lappeenranta has faced significant flood-related challenges due to its geographic vulnerability to extreme rainfall and snowmelt events. The available data on flood damages in the region, drawing on municipal records, hydrological studies, and national risk assessments. Historical Flood Damages and Economic Impacts in 2012, and May 2024 Flood Warnings is used as a context to the damages in case of flood event in the current analysis.

In 2012, one of the most well-documented flood events occurred, when prolonged rainfall and accelerated snowmelt led to severe flooding across the Saimaa basin. A national assessment estimated total damages in the Lappeenranta-Imatra region at €77 million that includes impacts in infrastructure, agricultural and residential property damage. In May 2024 Lake Saimaa’s water levels rose 75 cm above average, threatening low-lying structures, agricultural fields, and critical infrastructure. While no direct monetary damage figures were released, authorities identified:

¹⁹ https://vesi.fi/aineistopankki/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Raportteja_24_2023.pdf

²⁰ [https://pelastustoimi.fi/-/saimaan-pinta-noin-75-senttia-korkeammalla-kuin-normaalisti?doAsUserId=vQza02wL5k%3D%2Fsv%2Fen%2Fru%2Fru%2Fru%2Fru%2Fsv%2Fru%2Fsv%2Fen%2Fen%2Fru%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dfi_FI%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Den_US%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dfi_FI](https://pelastustoimi.fi/-/saimaan-pinta-noin-75-senttia-korkeammalla-kuin-normaalisti?doAsUserId=vQza02wL5k%3D%2Fsv%2Fen%2Fru%2Fru%2Fru%2Fru%2Fru%2Fsv%2Fru%2Fsv%2Fen%2Fen%2Fru%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dfi_FI%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Den_US%3Flanguageld%3Dsv_SE%3Flanguageld%3Dfi_FI)

²¹ [https://api.kwrwater.nl/uploads/2019/05/Nicklin-Leicher-Diepperink-van-Leeuwen-Understanding-the-costs-of-inaction-An-assessment-of-pluvial-flood-damages-in-two-European-cities-Water-\(Switzerland\)-11\(2019\)4-no.-801.pdf](https://api.kwrwater.nl/uploads/2019/05/Nicklin-Leicher-Diepperink-van-Leeuwen-Understanding-the-costs-of-inaction-An-assessment-of-pluvial-flood-damages-in-two-European-cities-Water-(Switzerland)-11(2019)4-no.-801.pdf)

²² <https://transformar.eu/storage/2024/11/TA-D4.3-Learning-story-on-NBS-and-Book-of-NBS.pdf>

²³ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/case-studies/protecting-surface-water-quality-in-lappeenranta>

²⁴ <https://lappeenranta.fi/en/news>

²⁵ https://wwwi9.ymparisto.fi/9/fi/tulvariskit_alueella/KASELY/04_Vuoksen_vesistöalue.pdf

²⁶ <https://www.sttinfo.fi/tiedote/70201057/saimaan-ja-vuoksen-juoksutussaannon-historian-suurimmat-juoksutukset-alkavat?publisherid=69817877&lang=fi>

- **At-risk infrastructure:** 15 km of regional roads (including segments of Highway 6), 12 bridges, and 3 wastewater treatment plants.
- **Agricultural vulnerability:** 500 hectares of spring crops (predominantly barley and oats) in flood-prone zones near the lake.

A 2024 pluvial flood modeling study for Finnish cities, including Lappeenranta, estimated that a single 60 mm/hour rainfall event could cause:

- **Direct damages:** €10–15 million to residential properties and commercial buildings.
- **Indirect costs:** €2–4 million in traffic disruptions, emergency response, and water contamination mitigation.

Table 5.9 Quantification of impacts of historic extreme events for city of Lappeenranta

	Description / Impact	Estimated Damages (€) ²⁷
2012 Flood Event	Infrastructure, agriculture, residential property	€77 million (Lappeenranta-Imatra region, 2011 price level)
May 2024 Flood Risk	At-risk infrastructure, crops, wastewater plants (no direct monetary figure reported)	-
Pluvial Flood Scenario	Modeled 60mm/hr rainfall event: property, commercial, indirect costs	€10–15 million (direct), €2–4 million (indirect)

Avoided damages assessment

Input data

In order to implement the sparse data availability approach a compilation of different type of data was compiled from different sources. Climate information were provided via WP2, D5.2 provided the solution effectiveness and historic damages information were gather via online resources. It is noted that climate information plots and analysis can be found in ANNEX II.

Table 5.10 Input data for historic period for city of Lappeenranta

	Variable	Value	Source
Historical climate data	Average annual extreme events	0.2	WP2
	Intensity index (1-5 scale)	min=23, max=68, avg=30	WP2
	Area population	73,320.00 (not used as no downscaled was performed)	Deliverables / Online sources
	Total area size [km2]	~1.72M	Deliverables / Online sources

²⁷ <https://recovery.preventionweb.net/media/100248/download>

		(not used as no downscaled was performed)	
	Climate risk index (0-1 scale)	0.2	WP2

Table 5.11 Input data for climate projections RCP26 for city of Lappeenranta

Low emissions future climate data	Variable	Value <i>(2071-2100 RCP26)</i>	Source
	Projected annual events	0.4	WP2
	Projected Intensity index stats	min=25, max=70, avg=34	WP2
	Population change factor	0.15	WP2

Table 5.12 Input data for climate projections RCP85 for city of Lappeenranta

High emissions future climate data	Variable	Value <i>(2071-2100 RCP85)</i>	Source
	Projected annual events	1	WP2
	Projected Intensity index stats	min=30, max=90, avg=40	WP2
	Population change factor	0.18	WP2

Table 5.13 Input data for solution efficiency and damage assessment for city of Lappeenranta

	Solution efficiency		Damage Factor [unit(e.g. €)/event/intensity unit]	
	Value	Source	Value	Source
Direct	-	D5.2 DB	€77 million €10–15 million	D3.5 <i>(previous section)</i>
Indirect	Economic_avg(RSP)=3.66 Enviromental_avg(RSP)=2.83	D5.2 DB	€2–4 million	D3.5 <i>(previous section)</i>
People	Socia_avg(RSP)=3.19	D5.2 DB	-	D3.5 <i>(previous section)</i>

Assessment

To perform the analysis and assess the avoided damages, the algorithm developed and described in D3.4 and published in ZENODO <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15324264> was used.

Table 5.14 Assessment results for city of Lappeenranta

Total avoided damages	Baseline (now)	RCP26	RCP85
No Solution implementation	3,384,000.0€	9,914,080.0€	24,785,200.0€
With Solution implementation	2,744,400.0€	8,045,928.0€	20,114,820.0€
Avoided damages	639,600.0€	1,868,152.0€	4,670,380.0€

In case of city of Lappeenranta, the avoided damages assessment with the sparse data approach yields 0.6M to 4.7M euros depending on the climate scenario. All damages derived from the indirect category as no data for damages were acquired for people category and no solution relevant to direct damages was applied. It is noted that the table above is provide the damages values alongside the avoided damages, whereas, the Figure below illustrated the avoided damages only.

Figure 5.4 Bar plot of avoided damages for city of Lappeenranta

6. Good and best practices guidelines for avoiding damages

The Avoided Damages assessment through the developed framework was applied to the demonstrators of TransformAr project with different results, in terms of success, and with different barriers that needed to be overcome. In most of the cases, the data quantity or quality was not enough in order to apply the High availability approach. In addition, the projections of KPIs to the future under different climate scenarios was not obvious with the lack of specialized tools or studies creating another barrier. In order to overcome the limitation, a sparse availability approach was developed (see D3.4) that provides an easy but less accurate way to estimate the avoided damages with and without a solution. The compiled experience, alongside the need to incorporate the current framework in the potential users' decision making, led to guidelines and best practices that optimize the process and help to the replicability of the framework of avoided damages. The good and best practices guidelines are based on a coherent methodical approach that is presented in a series of sequential steps:

1. Identify the Climate Avoided Damages team and support by local stakeholders and experts
2. Design the Avoided Damages Plan
3. Define the relevant climate hazard and climate scenario(s)
4. Describe the region via identification of the Environmental type
5. Identify relevant solutions
6. Determine the most impactful solutions (KPIs)
7. Build your solution portfolio
8. Assess the damages from Climate Change
9. Assess the avoided damages of proposed improvements
10. Report results and recommendations

Figure 5.1

Step 1. Identify the Climate Avoided Damages team support by local stakeholders and experts

An effective Avoided damages framework requires an interdisciplinary team with extensive knowledge and experience in various sectors alongside various levels of governance and supporting organizations. The team requires (1) a project lead that can manage the entire process and ensure the assessment and results are correct and (2) specialized experts in the fields of climate change adaptation / mitigation. Also, societal experts, urban planners, should be invited if needed.

Step 2. Plan the Avoided Damages Plan

Once the team is assembled, the project lead develops a project plan that outlines how the Avoided Damages assessment will be conducted. The project lead identifies team members' roles and responsibilities, develops the Avoided Damages assessment schedule, and gathers and distributes preliminary data and information to prepare for the health care facility characterization survey.

Step 3. Define the climate hazard

This step involves the identification of the (climate related) stressors and parameters that influence the area of interest. It involves analysis of the historic climate (and secondary hazard) data, future climate projections from existing databases and/or if this is required the provision of specialized simulations.

Step 4. Describe the region via identification of Environmental type

This step will identify and characterize the region likely to be affected by climate hazards and classified by the environmental type. The types are derived from TransformAr demonstrators' characterization but can be expanded with new cases.

Step 5. Identify relevant solutions

Based on the region description and hazard, the team can search in the TransformAr database to identify relevant solution. This will work as an initial solution list for building the portfolio of solutions to be assessed.

Step 6. Determine the most impactful solutions

This step builds on the list of solutions and provides a way to identify the most effective solutions based on previous cases. The score correlated with the solutions provide a way to order them according to their performance or information that the solutions may produce (e.g. sensors). In addition, the team based on member's experience and expert's opinion, performs an importance analysis towards assigning a score in each KPI (a_n) or category expert (direct, indirect, people) depending on approach chosen.

Step 7. Build your solution portfolio

Combining the list of solutions coming from previous steps, the team should contact local experts and stakeholders, and analyse national or regional adaptation strategies to filter the list and add new transformative solutions. The latter introduces the local experience into the solution suggestions, thus, developing a portfolio of solutions with local characteristics, ready to be used in the avoided damages assessment. It is noted that the new additions to the solution portfolio should be linked to a set of KPIs that will quantify their effectiveness.

Step 8. Assess the damages from climate change

This step applies the damages assessment for the current climate conditions (Bs) and for the future climate scenario(s) (CC). The team keeps following the TransformAr's avoided damages framework and provides values for the chosen KPIs in order to assess the direct, indirect and people damages for each hazard, without (nS) and with solution (S) implementation.

Step 9. Assess the avoided damages of proposed improvements

This step utilizes the information of different type of damages and applies the process to assess the avoided damages for short-term (avoided damages for current climate conditions between the no solution implementation and solution implementation, AD_{Bs}) and long-term (avoided damages between current climate conditions with no solution implementation and the future climate scenario with solution implementation, AD_{CC}).

Step 10. Report results and recommendations

The final step of the avoided damages assessment is reporting the results in a manner usable to the decision-makers responsible. The goal of the reporting phase is to provide accurate unbiased information that clearly and accurately defines the current state and provides potential solutions for short- and long-term adaptation.

The primary aim of the good and best practices guidelines for avoided damages assessment, is to provide a common ground, whereby different data sources (e.g. models, sensors, expert opinion) and diverse transformative solution can lead to the avoided damages estimation from climate change. To achieve this, the framework developed is generalized and customizable enough and the whole process can be characterized as relatively easy to be followed based on the steps presented that summarizes the experienced gained in the demonstrator's application.

7. Conclusions

In the context of the TransformAr project, the concepts of Damages and Avoided Damages from climate change are developed and defined based on current literature. Damages from climate change include a wide range of adverse impacts that are not sufficiently mitigated or adapted to, while avoided damages represent the benefits of effective mitigation and adaptation efforts, which prevent potential future impacts.

In the current deliverable, a framework was introduced to evaluate the effectiveness of TransformAr solutions by focusing on the concept of avoided damages. This framework quantifies effectiveness and damages either qualitatively or quantitatively using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs). The evaluation is conducted for both the current situation and future scenarios, comparing conditions before and after the implementation of the solutions. By comparing quantified values with and without the planned solutions across various climate scenarios, the assessment estimates the avoided climate damages. The framework was based on the work from 'D3.4 - Tools on the avoided damages and benefits per demo' and it was refined and expanded to more clearly define the concepts of damages and avoided damages. This development was based on discussions with demonstrators and technical partners and the experience gained through interactions with these stakeholders and overcoming various barriers.

For validating the overall approach, in the current deliverable a review of the current best practices and guidelines related to avoided damages from climate change was performed. In addition, a detailed presentation of the implementation of the avoided damages framework with the high availability approach (KPIs) for the case of Municipality of Egaleo (MOE) and Gjøvik, alongside two cases (West Country region and city of Lappenraanta) are included.

The avoided damages framework incorporates the elements of being generalized and flexible enough to fit a diverse list of solutions and being easy to replicate. Towards the replicability of the framework, good and best practices guidelines were introduced that is the result of implementing the framework during the TransformAr project. It can be considered an optimized way to implement the avoided damages framework without the barriers faced during the development. The guidelines are a series of ten steps written from the management and administration point of view, trying to avoid technical details that can be found in the methodology section.

In summary, the current report is a compilation of the knowledge and experience gained from demonstrators towards the transferability of the practices used for avoiding damages at regional scale to other cases.

References

- Geest, K., & Warner, K. (2019). Loss and damage in the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (Working Group II): a text-mining analysis. *Climate Policy*, 20, 729 - 742. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2019.1704678>.
- Voigt, C. (2008). State Responsibility for Climate Change Damages. *Nordic Journal of International Law*, 77, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1163/090273508X290672>.
- Hsiang, S., Kopp, R., Jina, A., Rising, J., Delgado, M., Mohan, S., Rasmussen, D., Muir-Wood, R., Wilson, P., Oppenheimer, M., Larsen, K., & Houser, T. (2017). Estimating economic damage from climate change in the United States. *Science*, 356, 1362 - 1369. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal4369>.
- Kooten, G. (2013). Economic Assessment of the Damages Caused by Global Warming. , 221-284. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4988-7_7.
- European Commission. (2021). Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. *European Commission*, 6(11), 951–952.
- Kuyper, J., Schroeder, H., & Linnér, B. O. (2018). The evolution of the UNFCCC. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 43, 343–368. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102017-030119>
- Leiter, T. (2021). Do governments track the implementation of national climate change adaptation plans? An evidence-based global stocktake of monitoring and evaluation systems. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 125(August), 179–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.08.017>
- Mantlana, K. B., Ndiitwani, M., & Ndhleve, S. (2024). A perspective on the significance of reporting climate change adaptation information to the united nations framework convention on climate change. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-024-09640-2>
- Oen, A. M. P. (2019). Nature-Based Solutions Are Gaining Momentum from International Initiatives Promoting Environmental, Social, and Economic Benefits. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 15(6), 830–831. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4203>
- Palutikof, J. P., Boulter, S. L., Field, C. B., Mach, K. J., Manning, M. R., Mastrandrea, M. D., Meyer, L., Minx, J. C., Pereira, J. J., Plattner, G.-K., Ribeiro, S. K., Sokona, Y., Stadler, F., & Swart, R. (2023). Enhancing the review process in global environmental assessments: The case of the IPCC. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 139, 118–129. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.10.012>
- Remling, E. (2018). Depoliticizing adaptation: a critical analysis of EU climate adaptation policy. *Environmental Politics*, 27(3), 477–497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2018.1429207>
- Rutherford, V. E., Hills, J. M., & Le Tissier, M. D. A. (2020). Comparative analysis of adaptation strategies for coastal climate change in North West Europe. *Marine Policy*, 111, 102478. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.07.005>

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

ANNEX I: Demonstrators profile

Municipality of Egaleo

The Municipality of Egaleo (MOE) will install smart climate stations (SCS) at key municipal buildings to acquire a view of the microclimatic conditions. A citizen's app (CAE) will allow inhabitants to participate in the debate around Climate Change (CC), the changes of the microclimate and potential solutions. Awareness-raising modules (AWAR) will be designed, especially for young people and school pupils to promote climate awareness. In addition, a climate innovation hub (CIH) will be installed to promote green and climate friendly entrepreneurship. A demand analysis for social services and infrastructures (DSI) will be conducted.

Sectors (KCS) impacted

Three KCS where the MOE demonstrator will be implementing solutions to adapt the impacts of climate change include **health**, **infrastructures**, and **urban planning**, described in more detail below:

Health

Rapid urbanization has led to a sharp increase in emissions of CO₂, NO_x and other pollutants, adding to the increasing intensity of heatwaves, significantly affecting the health of citizens. Green areas are extremely limited, leading to artificial means. Even if socially vulnerable groups amount to 10% of the population of the Municipality, this remains a huge problem. Climate change is expected to increase these groups and negatively affect their living conditions.

Infrastructures

Building and infrastructures are not climate-proof. Thunderstorms and heatwaves cannot be dealt with the existing infrastructure degraded each year.

Urban planning

Climate change also reinforces the urban heat island phenomenon in Egaleo, leading to an increase in energy consumption and carbon footprint; and causing faster degradation of asphalt, tarmac, concrete and another hard surfacing with more frequent needs for maintenance works. The phenomenon thus leads to a reduction in the absorption of rainwater, which overcomes stormwater systems and increases flood risks. Climate change combined with rapid urbanization has created the need for innovative and sustainable urban planning.

Description of the solutions

In TransformAr project MOE will build a series of solutions that work together complementary towards climate awareness and adaptation of MOE and its citizens (see *Figure 3*). MOE solutions comprise of data collection from various sources, analysis and post-processing of the data and feedback the outcomes to the citizens and promote climate awareness or utilize them for evidence informed climate adaptation policy suggestions at local municipality level. *Table 3.1.1* presents each solution of TransformAr for MOE.

Table 3.1.1: Description of MOE solution within TransformAr project

Solution	Description
Smart Climate Station - SCS	MOE focuses on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) around key areas of the city. The purpose of the SCSs is to gather real-time data regarding the micro-climate of the city, supporting the public administration office to ready the citizens in case of

	climate emergencies. After careful consideration and design, the key areas have been identified and the SCSs will begin their operation during the timeline of this demo. SCS will register Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure, CO2 (ppm), PM 2.5 /10 (ppm), Wind speed and Rainfall.
<i>Demand Social Analysis - DSI</i>	MOE provides a series of social/health services to the citizens. Due to climate change impact, the demand for such services, it is expected to change. To prepare to supply the services without interruption and meet the future demand, a demand analysis for social services/infrastructures will be performed. The analysis will provide the data to plan an adaptation strategy by taking into account the supply and demand of social services of the future.
<i>Citizen App – CAE</i>	MOE will develop a mobile app for gathering and distributed information; (1) it will be used to crowdsource data about climate awareness of citizens of MOE via questionnaire, (2) to disseminate TransformAr's MOE solution to the public and (3) to provide notifications for climate related events
<i>Awareness module - AWAR</i>	MOE will develop and test a curriculum of 45 min for pupils between 16-18 years old related to climate change understanding and climate awareness
<i>Climate Innovation Hub - CIH</i>	MOE will upgrade a multi-purpose facility to Climate Innovation Hub by (a) create a permanent exhibition about climate change and TransformAr solutions of MOE, (b) demonstrate live the data streaming from SCS and the post-processing indicators and (c) organizing a series of events for promoting the climate innovation (e.g. datathons), thus, providing access to the MOE's data and asking for innovative solutions for MOE's climate related problems.

The design and development of the MOE's ecosystem of solutions, is using SCS, CAE and DSI as data sources for weather, environmental, demographic and modelling result and AWAR, CAE and CIH as dissemination and communication frontends for the citizens of MOE. The management and analysis of the various types of datasets is accomplished with the support of NCSR D.

Overview of the expected impacts

The expected impacts per solution can be found in *Table 3.1.2*. The impacts are either direct, thus, they are deriving directly from the solution, or indirect, thus, they support the impacts of other solutions or long-term actions beyond TransformAr lifetime and scope.

Table 3.1.2: Description of expected impacts per solution

Solution	Expected impact
SCS	The data will provide a detailed dataset for weather and environmental conditions at MOE that will be visualized in Citizen Application Engagement (CAE) solution and disseminate part of the result to the citizens of MOE towards climate awareness in a large (municipality) level. The data will be used by the NCSR D (technical partner of MOE) to support the climate and environmental research of the organization and provide back to MOE a localized

	<p>and high-resolution weather forecast of 120 hours for the area of MOE. The forecast data will be used directly as an alarm system to inform the relevant Municipality Departments (Civil Protection, Municipal Police) and other First-Responders when abnormal temperature levels or precipitation levels are noted, helping to prevent casualties and loss of musicality social services.</p> <p>Beyond the MOE TransformAr solution, the SCS data collection will be used to monitor the effectiveness of different actions and measures implemented in MOE by comparison the measurement and relevant indicators before and after the implementation, thus, helping in quantify policy suggestion and making.</p>
<i>DSI</i>	<p>Forecasting the changes of demand for social services due to climate change, will enable the MOE to plan how the supply of social services will be maintain by meeting the demand and adapt on the new climate conditions and extreme events, such as more intense and frequent heatwaves.</p>
<i>CAE</i>	<p>As CAE provides a two-way channel of communication between MOE and citizens, it is expected to impact not only the citizen understanding of climate change, but also to provide a way to MOE to monitoring the impact of other TransformAr solution either directly (questionnaires with direct reference to specific solutions) or indirectly (overall quantification of climate awareness).</p>
<i>AWAR</i>	<p>AWAR is expected to impacted the climate change understanding of young people and try to clear misconceptions of what is climate change, what are the impacts, how it can be tackled etc. As such, it is aspired to create a more climate awared generation that pursuit for mitigation and adaptation through the municipality scale and/or social transformation.</p>
<i>CIH</i>	<p>CIH consist of (i) a static climate exhibition that is expected present the climate actions of MOE to the public; (ii) a dynamic part of livestreaming and visualization of the different types of data that are gathered and processed at MOE and both it is expected to impact people visiting the exhibition by raising the climate awareness. In addition, the availability of the dataset to SMEs, groups and teams via events (e.g. datathons) is expected to promote innovation and solutions for climate related problems that MOE has or will have in the future.</p>

Lappeenranta

Objectives of the Lappeenranta demonstrator are: (i) Urban surface runoff and flood mitigation, mitigation of the risk, (ii) Addressing the conveyance runoff water pipelines capacity issues, (iii) Increasing environmental awareness of emission load to recipient and groundwater, and mitigation of the load caused by the runoff, (iv) Increasing accessibility of data to all stakeholders via real-time monitoring and novel data, (v) Facilitation improvement of the choice of alternative options, e.g., green infrastructure, (vi) Increase awareness of stakeholders on climate change impacts on local level and region.

Sectors (KCS) impacted

For Lappeenranta, the Key Community Systems (KCS) that we focus on are water management and urban planning. Lappeenranta demonstrator will be implementing solutions to adapt to CC in these KCS described in more detail below:

Water management

Climate change impacts on water in Lappeenranta could create new water-related challenges and exacerbate existing ones in light of changing rainfall seasonality, climate variability and extreme weather events. This is likely to have a series of ramifications on a range of economic sectors that depend and rely on water such as tourism, industry, agriculture, among others. Not to mention, water quality could be affected as heavy rainfall could lead to the dilution of polluted water, which makes treating it more challenging and requires more costly and energy-intensive technologies. Therefore, addressing water issues and ensuring a sound water management is crucial for the city of Lappeenranta.

Urban planning

As the city of Lappeenranta is one of the major urban centres in the Saimaa region, urban planning needs to consider and adapt to climate change. Water from melting snow and flood water bring contaminants (e.g., oils, chemicals, microplastics, as well as organic and solid matters) which are likely to decrease the quality of water in the city and the lake. An adaptive urban planning could be a key to solve these issues and improve the living conditions of Lappeenranta's citizens.

Description of the solutions

Solution	Description
Nature based solution (URB)	Supported by LUT, LAPP will use NBS as part of the urban run-off system as a flood management solution. This will allow the co-design of new integrative Nature-Based Solutions as part of new urban adaptation standards which is jointly developed with city planners, architects, and urban architecture responsible administrators. Plants and greeneries will be used for reducing urban runoff.
Digital solution (SWMM)	LAPP, supported by LUT, VERHAERT and its Linked Third Party Pegus Digital, will couple a first set of new sensors, measuring water quality, flow and volume within the water pipe and drainage system, to a scalable digital platform. This platform will be developed to TRL level 7 to prove monitoring scalability & impact for Lappeenranta. Analysis of available and generated data of the purification/filtration processes and control processes of the runoff-water management system will be executed by LUT with initial research by VERHAERT on applicable predictive machine learning models.
Citizen app (CAF)	For the city of Lappeenranta, NTNU, together with LUT, will develop and support the implementation of a citizen application for crowd sensing and real time monitoring of anomalies due to climate change events.
Choice experiment (CEI)	Additionally, LAPP will also conduct choice experiments for the stormwater management system (in T4.4) upscaling. The outcome will be models for integrating knowledge on stakeholder preferences for climate adaptation and related services into the design of new policy instruments and business models and the co-design and test policy tools as part of new adaptation standards jointly with stakeholders, through behavioural economic

experiments in the different regions. For this specific case, the Gjøvik municipality will have 2 field trips to follow the implementation of such solutions to foresee a potential replication.

Overview of expected impacts

The expected impacts of solutions demonstrated are described in Table 5. All four solutions can be expected to have an impact on flood vulnerability, and social acceptance or acceptance in city planning. CAF and CEI can have long-term effects on water quality. However, in CAF and CEI the impact is not measured with indicators due to the nature of the impact. URB with monitoring system, and the influent together with the groundwater will be analyzed. This empirical information can be utilized together with existing water quality of recipient lake and wetlands to evaluate the impacts. Economic assessment and impacts in this frame will be done via empirical cost estimates and comparing to alternative solutions typically applied in Lappeenranta. Tables 5. and 6. describe the expected impacts and the indicators in detail.

Expected impact	URB	SWMM	CAF	CEI
Flood Vulnerability				
Gathering runoff (stormwater) from streets and leading them to biofiltration will help free capacity from drainage and mitigate flood and drought risks.	x			
Monitoring volume flows and surface levels provides novel information and warnings.		x		
Distributed stormwater management mitigate flood risks				
Distributed stormwater management mitigate flood risks	x	x		x
Realtime estimates for precipitation via cameras provide local estimates and warnings		x	x	
Water Quality				
Realtime monitoring of URB together with laboratory measurements provides information on runoff and groundwater quality.		x		
Biofiltering field utilizes nutrients and filters urban emissions	x			
Acceptance				
City planning gain novel information to support decision making and planning	x	x	x	x
Citizen's awareness of environmental effects of runoff and choices for mitigating the risks and impacts increase	x		x	x
Economic Costs				
Solution costs are compared to traditional alternatives and reflected to benefits expected.	x	x	x	x

Westcountry Region

Sector (KCS) impacted

The Westcountry is likely to witness drier summers and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events, such as droughts (Southwest Water 2021). High energy rainfall events can also cause mobilization of sediment and nutrients leading to water quality issues.

The Meteorological Office highlights detailed impacts for the Southwest (Met Office UKCP) including:

- More frequent intense rainfall and wind-driven rain causing river and surface water flooding.
- Warmer wetter winters causing problems with crop management.
- Hotter drier summers causing problems for water quality and supply.
- Increase in extreme weather and disruptive events such as flooding, droughts, landslides or heatwaves interrupting or limiting access to vital services and impacting on people's physical and mental health.
- Sea level rise affecting the viability of coastal communities and coastal infrastructure through flooding and erosion.

These projections were supported by the modelling carried out by PIK for the Westcountry stakeholder workshops for WP2.

Description of solutions

Solution	Description
<i>Riparian buffers with wetland restoration</i>	Riparian buffers are bankside strips along watercourses where agricultural activities are reduced or excluded. This is commonly done by constructing fencing to keep livestock off, or seeding grass at the edge of arable fields. The primary purpose is to protect rivers from direct impacts such as poaching by cattle and bank destabilisation, as well as nutrient input from fertilisers and dung. Studies (Vought et al 1995) have shown efficacy of buffers in removing nutrients increases with width, due to the rougher surface of vegetation capturing sediment and increasing infiltration due to root action and reduced compaction. This effect increases steeply to about 6m width and levels off at around 20m. The type of vegetation, soil properties, local climate and topography also play a role in buffer effectiveness. The adjacent land use will affect the level of nutrients entering the buffer. Buffer strips also provide space for riparian vegetation and woodland, which is considered an essential component of the river ecosystem. Currently, river condition assessments for BNG consider 10m width either side of the channel to be part of the river. WRT have found that fencing a narrow buffer (1-2m) where nutrient levels have already been elevated by agricultural management results in dense growth of brambles (<i>Rubus</i>) and nettles (<i>Urtica dioecia</i>). This limits opportunities for more varied natural vegetation to emerge. Another issue is the increasing colonisation by Invasive Non Native Species such as Himalayan Balsam (<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>), particularly associated with increased light levels from riparian management. It is therefore

Ponds and SuDS capturing sediment

considered beneficial to continue low levels of conservation grazing in these buffers in many cases. This requires a wider buffer to be practical. Examples of trial sites include Slaughterbridge Farm, Penvose campsite and Yarty Farm in the Camel catchment.

Introducing features to capture and manage overland flow helps treat nutrient pollution as well as flood risk. These need to be sited in a location near a source and on a pathway of likely flows during heavy rainfall. Typically, a sediment trap is a depression excavated for capturing soil run off, whereas a longer treatment train including swales, ponds and wetlands would be required for effective water quality improvements. Studies show that functional ponds (that stay wet) hold high levels of sediment at the bottom of the pond (Gilbert et al 2014). There is also evidence that this can capture carbon, contributing to climate change mitigation. There is a risk however that if the pond is not maintained and dries out, or banks fail, the nutrient rich sediment will be released back into surface waters, reversing these benefits. Similarly, if sediment builds up, seasonal changes in temperature and water volume can cause phosphates to be released into a soluble state which will escape through overflows or outlets. Therefore, it is essential that these features are regularly maintained, with sediment being removed from the system, to remain effective. Sediment can be spread on adjacent low risk land (level and away from watercourses), where they will contribute to soil and crop nutrient levels and become a useful resource. Maintenance activities should use straightforward techniques and equipment so that they can be carried out sustainably by the landowner.

Additional benefits from ponds and scrapes and other SuDS features include increased habitat for invertebrates, birds, amphibians and wetland plants. They improve infiltration rates and hold water for longer, reducing flood risks and improving drought resilience. High levels of nutrients entering the system will reduce the biodiversity benefits, as will overzealous maintenance activity, so a pragmatic balance needs to be found between delivering different benefits. Sites using this approach include Wambrook farm, Penvose campsite, Worthyvale Manor, Snowdon Hill and Harpford Bridge Farm.

Floodplain reconnection

A once common feature of our agricultural landscapes are floodplain meadows, which remain wet for long periods of time after inundation from adjacent watercourses. Floodplains have been disconnected from river channels in many places. The channel has become more incised through repeated dredging to facilitate faster flows of water. There are often floodbanks, either designed, or informal from dredged material, preventing water overflowing onto the floodplain. In addition, field drains are commonly dug into riverside fields to make them accessible for grazing all year round. Reconnecting the floodplain encourages

interchange of water, sediment and nutrients between the channel and the floodplain, which becomes a wetland environment, supporting managing flood risk, climate regulation, habitat provision, groundwater recharge and amenity. This can involve blocking drains; excavating scrapes to retain longer term pockets of water; introducing material such as wood or stone to the river channel to partially obstruct it or make it shallower and push high flows into the floodplain. Introducing more diverse vegetation, either planted or by natural regeneration, can also slow flows and increase infiltration and sediment capture, as it increases the roughness (runoff coefficient) of the surface over which flood water flows, slowing it down and increasing infiltration and sediment capture.

Floodplain reconnection is being trialled at sites including Tregooden Farm, Chubbs Farm and Rooke Farm.

ANNEX II: Climate analysis plot used in sparse data approach

West Country region

Historical

```
historical_data = { under historical climate
'avg_events_year': 0.2, # this is the once in 5 years drought
'min_intensity': 6 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 1 years drought
'avg_intensity': 35 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 5 years drought
'max_intensity': 70 # days of water stress above threshold in a 30 year event
'risk_index': 0.2 # risk index (0-1 scale) # it is the once in 5 years drought
}
```

SSP126

```
'low_emissions':{ under 2041-2070 SSP126 climate
'events': 0.5, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 2.5 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 30 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 1 years drought
'avg_intensity': 60 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 5 years drought
'max_intensity': 100 # days of water stress above threshold in a 30 year event
'population_growth': 0.15 # Population change factor
},
```

```
'low_emissions': { under 2071-2100 SSP126 climate
'events': 0.6, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 3 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 20 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 1 years drought
'avg_intensity': 45 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 5 years drought
'max_intensity': 80 # days of water stress above threshold in a 30 year event
'population_growth': 0.15 # Population change factor
},
```

SSP585

```
'high_emissions': { under 2041-2070 SSP585 climate
'events': 0.8, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 4 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 40 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 1 years drought
'avg_intensity': 75, # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 5 years drought
```



```
'max_intensity': 105 # days of water stress above threshold in a 30 year event  
'population_growth': 0.18  
}  
  
'high_emissions': { under 2071-2100 SSP585 climate  
'events': 1, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 5 of 5 years  
'min_intensity': 50 # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 1 years drought  
'avg_intensity': 80, # days of water stress above threshold in a once in 5 years drought  
'max_intensity': 130 # days of water stress above threshold in a 30 year event  
'population_growth': 0.18  
}
```


Empirical Return Levels (1971-2020)

Empirical Return Levels (1971-2020)

Empirical Return Levels (2041-2070)

Empirical Return Levels (2041-2070)

Empirical Return Levels (2041-2070)

Empirical Return Levels (2071-2100)

City of Lappeenranta

Historical

historical_data = { under historical climate

'avg_events_year': 0.2, # this is the once in 5 years rain


```
'min_intensity': 23 # once in 1 years rain
'avg_intensity': 30 # once in 5 years rain
'max_intensity': 68 # 30 year event
'risk_index': 0.2 # risk index (0-1 scale) # it is the once in 5 years rain
}
##### RCP26
'low_emissions':{ under 2041-2070 RCP26 climate
'events': 0.4, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 2 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 25 # in 1 years rain
'avg_intensity': 33 # once in 5 years rain
'max_intensity': 60 # 30 year event
'population_growth': 0.15 # Population change factor
},

'low_emissions': { under 2071-2100 RCP26 climate
'events': 0.4, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 2 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 25 # once in 1 years rain
'avg_intensity': 34 # once in 5 years rain
'max_intensity': 70 # 30 year event
'population_growth': 0.15 # Population change factor
},
##### RCP85
'high_emissions': { under 2041-2070 RCP85 climate
'events': 0.5, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 2.5 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 30 # once in 1 years rain
'avg_intensity': 40 # once in 5 years rain
'max_intensity': 100 # 30 year event
'population_growth': 0.18
}

'high_emissions': { under 2071-2100 RCP85 climate
'events': 1, # Under this climate the 5 year event would happen in 5 of 5 years
'min_intensity': 30 # once in 1 years rain
'avg_intensity': 40 # once in 5 years rain
'max_intensity': 90 # 30 year event
```


'population_growth': 0.18

}

TransformAr

www.transformar.eu

TransformAr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.